

MANUAL OF DATA SPECIFICATIONS REQUIRED FOR MAPPING OF ACTORS AT LIVING LABS

Deliverable 4.1

D4.1 Manual of Data Specifications required for mapping of actors at Living Labs

State of art and context of circular economy, challenges in circular regions and specific data required for each Living Lab

Summary

Objectives:

The main objective of Deliverable 4.1 is to define the context of circular economy in European cities, characterize existing available information from the Living Labs (LLs) related to circular economy and identify a **preliminary list of actors** and their interactions through **circular maps**. D4.1 seeks to provide a general **manual of data specifications and acquisition**, from a technical and a socio-economic view, focusing on **Water-Energy-Waste-Materials** from each LL, in order to define circular opportunities for LL owners and their stakeholders.

Additional objectives of this D4.1 are: 1) to define the circular economy implementation in the context of the challenges for future circular cities and 2) to characterize the taxonomy of LLs, identifying the **main stakeholders and their synergies and connections** (city council, water utilities, multisectorial companies, agricultural parks, natural parks, supramunicipal organisms, etc), their roles in the region and their relation through the Water-Energy-Waste-Materials nexus.

Methodology:

Within Task 4.1 from WP4, technical and socioeconomic information about **circular economy initiatives** has been collected and a preliminary **list of stakeholders** and **their circular maps** has been characterised for the 6 Living Labs: Alicante, Bodø, East Frisia, Flanders, Lisbon and Venice. D4.1 defines data that will be collected overall through MS05 and specifically through technical questionnaires prepared in Task 4.2, regarding: **water** (water balance, input quantity and quality data, distribution networks, wastewater treatments, reclaimed water, consumption and uses of water, etc.); **energy** (energy consumption and source, energy production, use of renewable energies, etc); **raw materials** (material flows, types and characteristics, etc); **waste** (waste generation, type of waste, valorization potential, waste treatments, etc.) and **current business models**. This Deliverable 4.1 will allow Work Package 4 to establish a **first roadmap** to start with the identification of **first circularities** (starting in March 2021) and it will be connected and complemented by MS03 “Guidelines to operate LLs and CoPs” and D1.1 “CoPs’ architecture and -final - stakeholder mapping for each LL” criteria during next months.

Results and findings:

A list of data and specification to identify circular opportunities based on Water-Energy-Waste-Materials nexus. Living Labs characterisation, evaluation of their regions taxonomy and preliminary identification of stakeholders to have a roadmap to identify circularities during Task 4.2.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

AdP	Águas de Portugal
AdTA	Águas do Tejo Atlântico
AEPSA	Associação das Empresas Portuguesas para o Sector do Ambiente
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMAEM	Aguas Municipalizadas de Alicante Empresa Mixta
APA	Agência Portuguesa do Ambiente
APDA	Associação Portuguesa de Distribuição e Drenagem de Águas
BGK	Bank Gospodarstwa Krajowego
BM	Business Model
BMC	Business Model Canvas
BWS	B-WaterSmart
CBM	Circular Business Model
CDC	Caisse des Dépôts et Consignations
CDP	Cassa Depositi e Prestiti
CE	Circular Economy
CEC	Circular Economy Club
CEID	Circular Economy Initiative Deutschland
CenSES	Centre for Sustainable Energy Studies
CETAQUA	Water Technology Centre
CF	Cohesion Fund
CM(L)	Câmara Municipal (Lisboa)
CoP	Community of Practice
CSCP	Collaborating Centre on Sustainable Consumption and Production
DSS	Decision Support System
EAFRD	European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development
EC	European Commission
EDR	Electrodialysis Reversal
EIB	European Investment Bank
EMFF	European Maritime and Fisheries Fund
ENEA	Agency for Energy Efficiency (Italy)
ENOVA	Norwegian Environment Agency
EPAL	Empresa Portuguesa Das Aguas Livres
EPSAR	Entitat Pública de Sanejament d'Aigües Residuals
ERDF	European Regional Development Fund
ERSAR	Entidade Reguladora dos Serviços de Águas e Resíduos
ESF	European Social Fund
ESG	Environmental, Social and Governance
ESIF	European Structural and Investment Fund
EU	European Union
GDP	Gross Domestic Product

GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GIS	Geographic Information System
Gt	Giga tonnes
ICO	Instituto de Crédito Oficial
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IDN	International Development Norway
IO	Input-Output
IWA	International Water Association
JICE	Joint Initiative on Circular Economy
KfW	Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau
LL	Living Labs
MFA	Material flow analysis
NBS	Nature Based Solution
NVE	Norwegian Water and Energy Directorate
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OFMSW	Organic Fraction of Municipal Solid Waste
OOWV	Oldenburgisch-Ostfriesischer Wasserverband
OVAM	Public Waste Agency of Flanders
PIF	Integrated Fusina Project
PSS	Product Service System
QMRA	Quantitative Microbial Risk Assessment
R&D	Research and Development
RO	Reverse Osmosis
RR	Resource Recovery
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
TLBMC	Triple Layered business model canvas
UF	Ultrafiltration
UN DESA	United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs
UNEP	United Nations Environmental Programme
UWOT	Urban Water Optioneering Tool
VMM	Flanders Environment Agency
WFD	Water Framework Directive
WP	Work Package
WRRF	Water Resource Recovery Facility
WS	Water Smart
WWR	Wastewater Reuse
WWTP	Wastewater Treatment Plant
ZEN	Zero Emission Neighbourhoods

Executive summary

By 2050, the global population is estimated to reach 9.7 billion people, 55% of which will be living in cities. The pressure on natural resources will increase, while new infrastructure, services and housing will be needed. Nowadays, cities represent almost two-thirds of global energy demand, produce up to 50% of solid waste and are responsible for 70% of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. The COVID-19 crisis highlighted the unsustainable nature of certain environmental and social trends and pushes us to reconsider the current production and consumption patterns towards a green recovery [OECD 2020] and to implement circular economy strategies. Circular Economy (CE) seems to be the best alternative for changing the linear economy model in cities and regions. The principles of CE are: **i) design out waste and pollution; ii) keep products and materials in use; and iii) regenerate natural systems.** It should allow to keep resources in use for as long as possible, extract the maximum value from them while in use, and then recover and regenerate products and materials at the end of each life cycle. In cities and regions, circular economy implies a shift in the way services are provided, making efficient use of natural resources as primary materials and optimising their reuse; in how economic activities are planned and carried out in a way to close, slow and narrow loops across value chains; and how infrastructure is designed and built to avoid linear lock-in and material waste. At the same time, circular economy is expected to generate positive impacts on the environment through reducing atmospheric emissions, increasing the share of renewable energy and recyclable resources, as well as reducing the use of raw materials, water, land and energy.

Applying **CE strategies in cities and regions** should bring in these positive impacts quicker than at national level. Therefore, in this project, circular economy insights will be applied in Living Labs (LL) from 6 coastal areas (Alicante, Bodø, East Frisia, Flanders, Lisbon, Venice). Specifically, WP4 goals are to identify regional or city potential for CE and to materialize specific CE models in each LL, including circular business models and circular financing opportunities, with focus on options that improve water-smartness, together with other strategies related to water, energy, resource recovery and waste. As the goal of Task 4.1 consists of identifying the current context of CE initiatives in the six LLs, we describe the LLs and map the main stakeholders involved in each one. In addition to the definition and identification of the main **stakeholders, who will be involved in the circularity in connection with the LLs owners, task 4.2 will identify CE indicators, while task 4.3 outlines new circular business models along the** along the different existing nexus between **water, energy, resource recovery and/or waste in each LL.**

The final chapter (4) of this Deliverable presents and discusses the data requirements and specifications required from all actors in each LL, as well including an Excel template that will be used to collect this information during T4.2.

Figure 1 shows the different steps to be followed in collecting the data, from information needs to final results. The upper part of the figure is related to the different steps for indicators and the bottom is related to the framework for action based on the compiled data. The middle part is the sequence to follow in order to achieve the results envisaged.

Figure 1: Procedure and framework of circularity data in the context of B-WaterSmart project.

Source: Cetaqua own elaboration.

1. **Goal and scope** - After the context definition (Chapter 1 and 2) and the characterization of each LL, followed by the definition of preliminary stakeholders and circular maps (Chapter 3), a relevant step is to define the specific goal(s) for each LL, as well as the scope that the project will seek to achieve in the context of circularity. Here, the proposal is to include the context of application, complementary methods and actions aimed at integrating stakeholders' views, impact on externalities, dependencies and influences.
2. **Inventory and data acquisition** - First, template questionnaires need to be elaborated for each Living Lab according to the request and definition detailed in the step 1 for each LL. These acquiring data will be collected during Task 4.2 for each stakeholder involved in each System study for each Living Lab according to the water-energy-waste-materials nexus and their current business models.
3. **Circularity identification** - From technical point of view, with information related to water-energy-waste-materials nexus among the system values and their stakeholders involved, new opportunities more circular to connect/adapt/propose their gaps will be identified for each Living Lab (task 4.2) with new/readapt business models (Task 4.3.).
4. **Circularity measurement** - To measure the circularity of opportunities identified in 6 Living Labs, several circular indicators will be defined through Deliverable 4.2 (Task 4.2, Task 4.3) to measure the circularities of circular opportunities identified. These circular indicators will take into account the three axes' indicators -environmental, economic, social viability according different typologies (water, energy, waste, material).
5. **Circularity assessment** - To quantify the circular assessment applying the indicators to the defined circularities to assure/evaluate their impacts and trade-offs, interpreting results to target audience and users of result intended application domain of the result provided from applying the framework. An action plan for each circularity in each Living Lab will be elaborated and their financial instruments identified (Task 4.4).

1. The circular economy in cities and regions

1.1. Introduction

Environmental problems, evolution of technology, increasing social disparities are some of the main transformations currently we need to cope with. The world's population continues to increase, but growth rates vary across regions. Based on UN prospects (World Population Prospects 2019), world's population is projected to grow from 7.7 billion in 2019 to 8.5 billion in 2030 (10% increase), and to 9.7 billion in 2050 (26%) and to 10.9 billion in 2100 (42%). Nevertheless, not all countries will contribute at same level and projected growth will be concentrated in just a few countries outside Europe (UN World Urbanization Prospects, DESA 2019).

Globally, more people live in urban areas than in rural areas, with 55% of the world's population residing in urban areas in 2018. In 1950, 30% of the world's population was urban, and by 2050, 68% of the world's population is projected to be urban. Specifically, in Europe growth rates of urban agglomeration will be mainly less of 1% (DESA, 2018) but more than 60% is urban.

These **urban spaces** are covering 7% of land area and are using 75% of annual **resource use**, 75% of **carbon emissions**, 80% of **energy consumption** and are generating 70% of global **waste consumption** (UN DESA, 2014, UNEP 2013). The resolution of this situation faces important challenges for cities. Although life satisfaction and living standards are highest in the cities (OECD/European Commission ,2020), therefore, pressures on natural resources and in the provision of new services, housing and infrastructures will be challenging. Urban areas and cities, more in coastal areas, are increasingly more vulnerable to **climate change** effects putting resilience actions in policy agenda. Consequently, impacts on cities sustainability should be in mind and efforts to decouple urban growth from both consumption and pollution are **motivating circular economy** (CE) strategies. Urban growth is related to the three dimensions of sustainable development: **economic, social and environmental** and for well-managing urbanization, population trends need to inform policies. In other words, agglomeration has positive externalities but also negative and these needs to be minimized. Examples are environmental degradation, air pollution, noise, isolation, and poverty.

This situation impacts on sustainability although policies should try to minimize them. New visions lay on the integration of economic model with environmental limits and social needs. There is a relationship between sustainable development and circular economy as, Bonato *et al.* (2018) suggest when labelling **urban circular economy** as *The New Frontier for European Cities' Sustainable Development*. In fact, the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) incorporate this vision and, specifically, highlight the need to ensure cities are safe and sustainable for all. In fact, SDG 11: *Sustainable cities and communities* are the basis for action. The goal for this SDG is defined as **making cities inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable**. For reaching the objective, **innovation** plays a fundamental role for improving **interaction with nature, new business models including social inclusion** as well as **technology** as enabler.

Based on the circular economy approach, there are more links with other Sustainable Development Goals. Specifically, with **SDG 12**, allowing for more sustainable and responsible consumption and production patterns. Moreover, it is also equally relevant for the achievement of **SDG 6** (clean water and sanitation), **SDG 7** (affordable and clean energy), **SDG 13** (climate action) and **SDG 15** (life on land) and, of course, for the **SDG 11**. Also, for **SDG 2**, zero hunger, **SDG 8**, decent work and economic growth, **SDG 9**, industry innovation and infrastructure and **SDG 14**, life below water with specific interest for coastal cities.

Unfortunately, **COVID-19** is having important negative impacts on most SDG except for **the reduction of some environmental impacts** due to economic activity decrease. In case of SDG 11, a mixed or moderately negative impact in the short-term is assessed in Sachs et al., 2020. Impacts are rising in urban poverty and vulnerability, lower access to public and green spaces, movements of population, reduction in pollution levels in short term and, finally, important problems in public transport. Yet, to date, the long-term impacts of the pandemic are unclear and uncertain.

This deliverable D4.1. is presented as follows. The first chapter is devoted to **discussing circular economy** in cities and regions, including business models for circular economy. The second chapter is about **water circular economy** in cities and regions. The third chapter describes **the six living labs** where a circular economy will be developed. Finally, the fourth chapter is focused on the kind of **data that living labs should collect** for designing and assessing circular economy opportunities and their actions plans for implementing CE in their cities or regions.

1.2. Circular Economy Strategy

In recent years, circular economy is emerging as a different approach for driving sustainable development. Both the definition and importance of CE are gaining momentum as a new way of acting. Sustainability implies bringing together economic development, environmental sustainability and social inclusion. This holistic perspective is necessary, since technology is not enough to solve potential complex and wicked problems, especially in the case of cities. But technology is not enough, it is necessary to have a holistic perspective, and this is even more important in the case of cities.

A circular economy is a systemic approach to businesses, society, and the environment. In contrast to the 'take-make-dispose' linear economy, a circular economy is restorative and regenerative by design and aims to decouple economic development from consumption of resources. It is based on three principles i.e., **to design out the waste and pollution, keeping the products and materials in use, and to regenerate natural systems.**

Since 2010, the **Ellen MacArthur** Foundation has significantly contributed to the development of CE practices in multiple sectors such as waste management, sustainable design and construction, food production, development indicators, etc. (EMF, 2017). The model distinguishes between **technical and biological cycles.**

In a complete circular economy, consumption happens only in **biological cycles**, where food and biologically based materials (e.g., cotton or wood) feed back into the system through processes such as composting and anaerobic digestion. These cycles **regenerate living systems** (e.g., soil), which provide **renewable resources for the economy. Technical cycles** recover and **restore products, components and materials** through strategies including **reuse, repair, remanufacture** or recycling. The Foundation depicts how every product needs to be designed taking into consideration both the technical and biological cycles involved in the manufacturing process.

Figure 2: Circular Economy Systems Diagram.

Source: Ellen Mc Arthur Foundation.

It is important to note that the circular economy is not an end per se but is a way of doing that will drive to an end. For this reason, **cities and regions**, as a key agent of change, should include this perspective and going beyond the shift towards sustainable production and consumption, having in mind business and governance models. Therefore, circular economy in cities has a huge potential and is a guiding way expressed by OECD (2020) under the **3Ps (people, policies and places)** framework. The OECD analytical framework [OECD 2020] lies on the cited megatrends (demographic growth, urbanization, climate change, economic issues), using opportunities (technological, socio-economic and environmental) for a system change (people, policies, places). It could be added that the COVID-19 and its effects highlighted the unsustainable nature of the same trends, making the **transition to a circular economy** even more urgent.

Nevertheless, CE cannot be identified with just one or some specific sectors or only in one phase of the **value chain**. Circular economy should transform all sectors and all phases of the value chain. The COVID-19 impact is changing the current paradigm and it is not clear what will be the economic evolution. Based on a long-term recovery for more inclusive, **green and smart cities** and concerning investments, the emphasis is on **environmental sustainability** and, specifically, on clean forms of urban mobility and energy efficiency focusing on the transition to a low-carbon and climate resilient

economy, well-being and inclusive growth. Although the impact of the crisis is very relevant, provision of funds is important too and we need to keep an eye on designing and **implementing CE strategies in cities**.

1.2.1 European Commission's Vision for Circular Economy

To decouple economic growth and development from resource consumption, the alternative model of CE is being promoted by the European Commission, with an aim to achieving resource efficiency, reduce waste production and improve environmental, economic and social sustainability (European Commission, 2015). Currently, the European Commission is strongly committed with circular economy along the lines of the EU **Circular Economy Action Plan** (2020)¹, which attributes an important role to cities and local territories in implementing the transition towards a CE model as one of the main pillars of the **European Green Deal (2019)**, the new agenda for sustainable growth in Europe. Building on the work done since 2015, this new Plan focuses on the design and production with a CE perspective, with the aim to ensure that the resources used are kept in the EU economy for as long as possible. The plan and the initiatives therein will be developed with the close involvement of the business and stakeholder community.

With measures along the entire life cycle of products, the new **Action Plan** aims to make our economy fit for a green future, strengthen our competitiveness while protecting the environment and give new rights to consumers. The initiative aims at boosting the production of sustainable products, empowering consumers, focusing on sectors with high circularity potential (e.g., information and communication technology (ICT), batteries, packaging, food, construction, textiles and plastics) and reducing waste. The initiative presents an outline with new measures to be implemented between 2020 and 2022 and includes a section on cities and regions. Applying CE measures in Europe is expected to increase the EU's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) by an additional 0.5% by 2030 and to create approximately 700,000 new jobs.

Concerning specifically cities and regions, the proposed European Urban Initiative², **the Intelligent Cities Challenge Initiative**,³ and the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative⁴ are expected to assist cities in specific areas, as well as the **Circular Cities Declaration**⁵. Furthermore, CE will be included among the priorities of the Green City Accord, the movement of European cities to engage in action towards meeting the EU's environment objectives (OECD, 2020). It is important to add that the Commission, in its European Semester Framework, will reinforce monitoring of country plans in the way of accelerating the transition to a circular economy. Hence, the Commission will update the monitoring framework, adding and developing new indicators on resource use, including consumption and material footprints. Finally, **the Action Plan** requires the cooperation of all stakeholders at all levels. In other words, in the context of cities, a good **mapping of stakeholders** becomes central in a CE strategy. As a result of the action plan, the EU will change how it is producing and consuming, while leading the way to become **climate-neutral**, through creating a competitive economy with more empowered consumers.

¹ COM (2020) 98 final. A new Circular Economy Action Plan. For a cleaner and more competitive Europe

² https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/newsroom/news/2019/03/20-03-2019-european-urban-initiative-post-2020-the-commission-proposal (accessed 18 January 2021)

³ <https://www.intelligentcitieschallenge.eu/> (accessed 18 January 2021).

⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/research-area/environment/circular-economy/circular-cities-and-regions-initiative_en (accessed 18 January 2021). Initiative supporting the implementation of local and regional circular economy solutions, funding, documents and latest.

⁵ <https://circularcitiesdeclaration.eu/>.

All the **circular opportunities** will be identified during Task 4.2. for each LL, inspired and in alignment with the circular economy strategies and EU Plans. Expected circular opportunities will be identified during T4.2 following the approval of the **Circular Economy Package** (EC, 2015). The EC made available in 2018 a monitoring framework that aims to measure the progress of the circular economy in all stages of the life cycle of resources, products and services, following the monitoring framework complements, the existing **Resource Efficiency Scoreboard** (EC, 2014) and **Raw Materials Scoreboard** (EC, 2016) and including **social innovations, eco-innovations, sharing economy initiatives, the level of greening of the main economic sectors, new business models' implementation, eco-design and architecture initiatives** (Avdiushchenko, 2018), as well as the **EC New Circular Economy Action Plan** mentioned before (EC, 2020). As such, it is expected to focus on **material footprints**, additional critical sectors (e.g., constructions, plastics, textiles, and electronics), the **design of sustainable products, innovation, added-value change and its implication for the climate neutrality ambition** of the EU (OECD, 2020).

Although several countries have developed **circular economy strategies at a national level**, few of them have set up a monitoring framework yet. In general, many of **these indicators** are focused on waste management. For example, **circular indicators** are generally used to monitor the progress on the targets that have been selected in their corresponding initiatives. For example, the **Action Plan for Circular Economy in Portugal 2017-2020** contains indicators to measure the progress of the ten lines of action set out in its strategy for the macro, meso and micro levels (Government of Portugal, 2017). Across various European countries, the national monitoring systems are mostly based on the EC Monitoring Framework. In Spain, **the Circular Economy Strategy of Spain**, approved in 2020, collects a series of indicators proposed by the EU. Furthermore, it also contains two additional indicators compared to the EU framework: the contribution of GHG in the waste sector measured in CO₂-eq (kt) and the preparation for reuse of waste (Government of Spain, 2020). In the **Netherlands**, the monitoring system for the circular economy, "**Circular economy: What we want to know and can measure**", is also inspired by the EC proposals for monitoring the circular economy (Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency, 2018). The strategy includes a wide variety of suggested indicators and an overview of relevant indicators to measure progress in the circular transition. Similarly, in **Italy**, **the report Towards a Model of Circular Economy for Italy** (Government of Italy, 2017) refers to the set of indicators proposed by the EC for the macro level and suggests a set of aspects that are necessary to be considered for the micro level: environmental impacts, resources used and economic value of resources. **Norway** has been working in the **Norway's first national strategy for a circular economy** focus on the development of a green, circular economy that makes better use of resources, and prepare a national strategy on the circular economy in late autumn 2020-**(The Norwegian Government declaration, Granavolden)**.

In sum, **circular database and indicator frameworks** are still not developed for some national strategies or are still in development. Hence, one of the objectives set by the strategy is to develop indicators, set specific targets and collect the appropriate data.

1.2.2 Cities and Circular Economy Challenges

In order to continue growing and increasing **liveability of the cities, as well as improve their resilience**, while minimising **unsustainable consequences** introduced previously, the strategy based on a shift **towards circular economy** is seen as a good solution. Therefore, we can introduce a **new development model for cities based on circular economy**. The introduction of *circular cities* goes

in hand with urban sustainability initiatives aimed to resolve defined problems, including, in the case of the EU, partnerships with multiple stakeholders (Prendeville *et al.*, 2018). However, the approach of cities to the circular economy aims, basically, to resolve local issues, although the impacts are in a wider scale.

The UNEP is working on sustainable cities and is focusing in different areas, while their approaches are based on circular economy principles, such as resource efficient cities, clean cities and Green and Healthy cities.

A circular city will likely include the following elements (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2017a) because all of them are present in every city (Figure 3) (Dhawan and Beckmann 2019):

- **A built environment** that is designed in a modular and flexible manner, sourcing healthy materials that improve the life quality of the residents, and minimise virgin material use. It will be built using efficient construction techniques, and will be highly utilised thanks to shared, flexible and modular office spaces and housing. Components of buildings will be maintained and renewed when needed, while buildings will be used where possible to generate, rather than consume, power and food by facilitating closed loops of water, nutrients, materials, and energy, to mimic natural cycles. These new approaches to creating buildings require innovation in design, technology and economic aspects.
- **Energy systems** are fundamental for industrial and residential energy consumption, transport and heating and cooling systems that are resilient, renewable, localised, distributed and allow an effective energy use, reducing costs and having a positive impact on the environment.
- An **urban mobility** system that is accessible, affordable, and effective. A multi-modal mobility structure that will incorporate public transportation, with on-demand cars as a flexible last-mile solution. Transportation will be electric-powered, shared, and automated. Air pollution and congestion will belong in the past, and excessive road infrastructure will be converted to serve other needs of citizens. Central to vehicle design will be remanufacturing, durability, efficiency and easy maintenance.
- An **urban bioeconomy** where nutrients will be returned to the soil in an appropriate manner, while generating value and minimising food waste. Nutrients could be captured within the organic fraction of municipal solid waste and wastewater streams and processed to be returned to the soil in forms such as organic fertiliser – used for both urban and rural agriculture. Through urban farming, the city will be able to supply some of its own food, reusing food waste and sewage in closed and local loops to produce vegetables, fruit, and fish. Such a system could also provide a more resilient, diversified and cost-effective energy system in the city through the generation of electricity from wastewater, biofuels and biorefineries. These will offer additional revenue streams to the city, capitalising on the utilisation of material and nutrients that are already in use.
- **Production systems** that encourage the creation of 'local value loops'. This means more local production and increased and more diverse exchanges of value in local economies. Maker-labs (to encourage local production, repair, and distributive manufacturing), collective resource banks (to even out the demand and supply of materials) and digital applications (to broker the exchange of goods, materials, and services) would feature in these local, circular production systems.

Figure 3: Elements for a circular city.
Source: Dhawan, P.; Beckmann; J. (2019).

Additionally, the transition would need (Dhawan, P.; Beckmann; J. 2019):

- **Circular Economy Legislation and policies**

A different legislation is necessary for changing production and consumption. Design and use incentives for changing behaviours need to be explored, and governments have an important role in influencing prices through economic instruments (taxes and subsidies).

- **Awareness, Education and Research**

Society needs to get clear and understandable information but without environmental awareness and knowledge it is a difficult task. Provide and disseminate knowledge, transform education and doing research are key issues for transitioning well towards circular cities.

Nevertheless, we cannot forget that technology has a role in enabling circular cities and, more specifically, digital technologies as, for example, Artificial Intelligence (AI) (EMF and Google, 2019) applied in food and consumer electronics value chains.

1.2.3 Towards a circular economy: key drivers for the circular economy transition in cities

Cities and regions hold core competencies for most policy areas underlying the circular economy. This includes **water, solid waste, built environment, land use or climate change**. In the buildings sector, for example, cities can operate buildings and housing, and enforce regulation on commercial and residential buildings, in favour of efficient energy performance policies. For solid waste, cities exercise powers in collection, treatment, cleaning, as well as in communication and information. Cities have powers over **water management**, operating infrastructures and incentivising water efficiency, amongst others. Cities and regions can approve land use planning and policies, including zoning, redevelopment and regeneration, encourage farmers' markets and commercial urban food production and develop climate adaptation plans (C40, 2011).

Although cities hold these capacities and management knowledge, it is important to know what the drivers of cities are, in order to base the action and support cities in the transition **towards circular economy**. OECD carried on a survey for knowing cities opinion on this (OECD, 2020a). According the results of the survey, major drivers for surveyed cities and regions to transition to a circular economy

are climate **change, global agendas and economic changes**. Even so, it is possible to group different drivers into environmental, institutional and socio-economic.

Environmental drivers

Cities are vulnerable to impacts of climate change, but they are contributing to climate risks too. For this reason, climate change is a driver for the circular economy. It is well known that there is a strong commitment about the achievement of the objectives of the Paris Agreement under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change to limit global warming to less than 2°C or 1.5°C by 2050.

Related to materials, OECD (2019) indicates that global material use is projected to more than double in 2060 (from 89 Gt in 2017 to 167 Gt), and if recycling is projected to grow there is a significant opportunity to potentially reduce emissions through effective materials management policies, prevention of material consumption, eco-design and reuse.

Institutional drivers

Global agendas are drivers for the transition to the circular economy. In fact, a circular economy supports, as we discussed, the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (increasing sustainability in cities, SDG11, and related SDG 12, 6, 7 and 15 and transversal ones), as well as the European Climate Action, the Paris Agreement under the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change, the New Urban Agenda (2016), the European Green Deal and G20 initiatives on resource efficiency.

Socio-economic drivers

Socio economic drivers include socio-economic changes, growing population and technological trends. The COVID-19 crisis has implied important GDP losses added to social impacts and the current climate problems. However, it is expected that 600 cities will generate nearly 65% of the world's economic growth by 2025 (McKinsey Global Institute, 2012). Concerning population, we have included in the introduction a discussion about its trends towards urban concentration. McKinsey (2018), imagining **the cities of future**, points out the role of an increasing population and the impact in the city's evolution from the shift from a rural to an urban context. In regards to technological trends, the survey accounts for more than 40% new business models, technical developments and R&D as a driver for transition to circular economy in cities. There are multiple examples of development and application of reverse logistic, leasing, sharing and other **business models** that are included in the document. McKinsey (2018) discusses 12 potentially disruptive technologies that should act as drivers for a circular economy, specifically digital technologies that can help to increase virtualization, dematerialisation, transparency on product use and material flows, as well as **feedback-driven intelligence**. It is important to insist that de implementation of these technologies requires collecting and analysing an important amount of data, not only on materials but also on social contexts and external conditions.

1.2.4 Some barriers and gaps for circular economy transition in cities

In Campbell-Johnston *et al.* (2019) we find a discussion (Figure 4) about **barriers and limits of cities' transition**. Barriers are divided in two groups: **hard and soft barriers**.

Technological and market/financial barriers are included as hard barriers. Concerning technological and technical barriers, transition is not easy because the knowledge of technologies and their application should evolve to circular ones. **Market and Financial barriers** are mainly based on

building a market for the second material supply, as well as making viable case for CE businesses.

Soft barriers include **institutional and regulatory** ones. In some cases, monitoring systems using suitable indicators and parameters for success are not in place. Cultural barriers concern a mind-shift in how consumers and producers are thinking and, finally, barriers based on a city level scale.

However, **cities and countries** are not homogeneous and more and different barriers appear. But an important issue is to know where cities are and which stage are they in the circular economy transition. In relation to possible obstacles emerging in the transition towards circular economy in cities, OECD (2020) points out five main gaps:

- **Funding gaps:** As the transition implies investments and good incentives, having sufficient financial resources, allowable financial risks, a scale adequate for action and the involvement of private investment became compulsory.
- **Regulatory gaps,** due to current regulations not being adapted and specifically developed for a circular economy. Usually, regulation is inadequate and, in some cases, incoherent across all levels of government and in the cities too.
- **Policy gaps** come from partial vision, bad leadership and coordination problems. In some cases, there is not sufficient involvement from politicians.
- **Awareness gaps** come from cultural issues and inadequate information related to all stakeholders.
- **Capacity gaps** are based on human resources and in technical solutions and, if they are not available, the transition will be difficult.

Figure 4: Governance gaps for a circular economy in cities and regions. Source: From OECD (2020).

1.2.5 From ideas to action for circular economy transition in cities

Taking action for a circular economy transition in cities is not an easy task. Dhawan and Beckmann (2019) in the “Circular Economy Guidebook for Cities” offer examples of mechanisms and initiatives that could be implemented. However, we can’t forget that cities are different between them, and the same strategy might not work for all.

The circular city approach should include adequate financing capacity, otherwise it will be very difficult to make the transition to a circular economy. In this sense, a document from European Investment Bank (EIB, 2018) offers its own view on the circular cities of tomorrow (Figure 10). We realise that there are not important differences between views coming from different institutions. This is a sign of the broad consensus about the aspects to be covered and introduced in any circular city strategy.

Figure 5: Circular city of tomorrow.

Source: EIB (2018) page 5.

Although, in the context of the B-WaterSmart project, the figure is not complete because water and waste, for example, are not included, the figure allows us to have a good idea about the complexity of cities’ circular economy and all the areas involved.

Dhawan and Beckmann (2019), based on the activities boosted by smart cities, propose a step process in order to go towards circular cities:

1. Defining a vision

For becoming a circular city that will give important benefits to the citizens, a clear vision and a strong **leadership** is necessary.

2. Circularity Roadmap

The roadmap should focus on key areas. For example, Amsterdam has **Prioritize regenerative resources**, **Design for the future**, Preserve and extend what’s already made, **Rethink the business model**, incorporate digital technology, use waste as resource and collaborate to create **joint value** as key points in the action plan. It is important that the roadmap is designed with the **stakeholder’s contribution**.

3. Map and document circular economy initiatives

There are different projects that could help cities in knowing circular cities initiatives. The idea is to include all initiatives coming from actions in the city by industries, services or public initiatives concerning the value chain. Going from design, materials manufacturing, logistic, sales, business models, product life extension, recycling, packaging, regulation or governance. In case there are no current initiatives, the idea is to develop plans and solutions for designing solutions to detected problems.

4. Tools and methodologies to quantify circular economy

There are some agreements about the methodology used. **Urban metabolism** is a good approach because it helps us to understand the dynamic of a city as a system. In fact, understanding urban metabolism allows us to **quantify energy, water and resources consumption** in order to know how energy, water or other resources are consumed in a city. Also, urban metabolism allows the incorporation of socioeconomic and policy analysis, as well as a life cycle approach. **Material flow analysis (MFA)** and **Input-Output (IO)** accounting are useful tools that can be used.

5. Circular Strategy

Although there are a lot of circular strategies at country level, circular strategies at city level are not generalised. Some examples, as Amsterdam, Peterborough, Rotterdam or Glasgow, are being analysed but we need to extend it to more and more cities.

6. Develop demonstration projects and set clear targets

Although we still have narrow evidence about the impacts of circular economy, we need to progress and build confidence about existing projects and implement new ones. Setting clear targets is important in order to allow progress monitoring.

7. Measure progress

Usually, we say that *what is not measured does not exist* and this is applicable to the circular economy implementation and evolution. For this reason, a **system of indicators** for assessing the implementation of **circular economy is compulsory**. There is a body of literature focused on setting performance indicators (e.g. Nika et al., 2020 including those for the urban water sector, or e.g. Kayal et al., 2019 for one synthetic indicator for measuring a firm's circularity in the water industry).

On the other hand, the list of 15 steps included in the approach of the European Investment Bank (EIB, 2018) will be presented under the four main basic phases for cities in the CE approach: **Plan, Act, Mobilise and Monitor**.

Planning is important and it is obvious that is the first question to be developed. It is important to remark the administration of the city should map a circular change with all relevant stakeholders. It includes the tree following actions:

- 1. Characterise and analyse local context and resource flows and identify idle assets:** The circular transition is focused on the economic and industrial profile of the city. The action is based on the identification of sectors (or companies) with a high level, now and in the future, of waste, the level of use of different assets and the capacity **to minimise waste** and use it as input in other companies or industrial processes, with the idea of **closing material loops** in mind. This is a hard work and, as we said, we need to analyse the urban metabolism and map all resource flows. These are difficult tasks, which require the support of all stakeholders involved in the process.
- 2. Conceptualise options and prioritise among sectors with circular potential:** For being successful, circular cities usually identify a few target sectors that are important in their **socio-economic** context and have a high potential. Commonly, sectors are construction, food and beverages, trade, electric and electronic equipment, and textiles.
- 3. Craft a circular vision and strategy with clear circular goals and targets:** A circular vision for the circular transition will serve as a guiding light for further strategic planning and implementation. Defining this vision should be done in a participatory manner, ensuring involvement and buy-in from all relevant stakeholders. The circular vision provides the basis for preparation of a **strategy for the circular transition with goals and targets** for development and division of tasks and responsibilities for all stakeholders. The strategy should cover all relevant city functions and services, as well as the identified target sectors and business activities with circular potential. The preparation of the strategy should involve all **relevant stakeholders** (for example **citizens, businesses, research and teaching institutions, media and the civil society**) and offer opportunities for awareness building and for fostering a culture of collaboration.

Acting devotes to pass from **strategic agenda** (defining in WP1 in the context of the B-WaterSmart project) to **specific measures** in order to be implemented through different **key actions (they will be proposed during task 4.2.)**.

- 4. Close loops by connecting waste/residue/water/heat generators with off-takers and users of such secondary resources:** The urban metabolism study prepared as a basis for the strategy will identify local value loops that can be closed. The interactions between all those possible involved is important including the collection and recycling of organic waste streams and by-products for use in biorefineries, urban farms or for energy production, with residues returned to soils.
- 5. Consider options for extending use and life of idle assets and products:** This measure can be achieved by establishing reuse and repair centres, helping companies to go from linear sale of products to new sharing, leasing and product-as-service business models, and by repurposing or promoting the sharing of idle and abandoned buildings and other assets. The goal is not only to save costs, but also extend the life and utility of assets and products and facilitate value recovery at end-of-life. At this respect, setting reverse logistic networks should act as enabler for facilitating the return and take-back of products for repair and remanufacturing.
- 6. Construct and procure circular buildings, energy and mobility systems:** As the urbanization is growing, demand for new buildings, energy and mobility systems is growing. The demand for new buildings should be met by planning, procuring and constructing circular buildings. Such buildings are flexible and modular, designed for extending their life, using

materials that allow the disassembly instead of demolition to facilitate reuse and recycling. Concerning energy, the use of renewable energy sources based on local generation and, finally, mobility systems should be shared, and where possible automated and on-demand.

7. **Conduct circular experimentation – address urban problems with circular solutions:** City administrations should instead encourage testing and experimentation with new circular concepts, approaches and business models establishing circular labs and possibly a flexible regulatory framework under which new business models can be developed and tested. By **establishing circular support hubs or similar**, cities can encourage and help entrepreneurs to develop their circular ideas into viable businesses
8. **Catalyse circular development through regulation, incentives and financing:** Regulatory actions and incentives design should be used as tools and levers for circular change. **City administrations** have an important role in supporting and securing access to financing.
9. **Create markets and demand for circular products and services:** One of the instruments used for creating markets is public procurement. By applying circular principles and criteria in procurement of construction, products and services, city administrations can contribute to generate demand. In a general way, including **circular economy requirements in the city procurement criteria** or through voluntary pledge programmes is a basic action.
10. **Capitalise on new ICT tools supporting circular business models:** Digital tools such as asset or material exchanges where supply and demand can be matched should be developed. In general, smart city developments could go in hand with circular economy requirements concerning tools.

Finally, and related to **monitoring of the measures and mobilisation of different agents**, the proposed steps are:

11. **Coach and educate citizens, businesses, civil society and media:** Progress towards a circular economy does not happen solely in city administration offices, but also through creative ideas and entrepreneurial efforts in homes, offices and companies.
12. **Confront and challenge linear inertia, stressing linear risks and highlighting circular opportunities:** Although there are people and companies whose behaviour is based on linear economy, increasing awareness about the implications of resource scarcity, rising prices and volatility, competition from innovative circular companies, increased customer concerns and awareness, and potential regulatory changes, should modify perception of linear risks and towards circular opportunities.
13. **Connect and facilitate cooperation among circular stakeholders:** As circular developments imply exchanges between different value chains, if there is some form of cooperation the action will be easier. In fact, cities can help to **connect different stakeholders** by involving them and by establishing, for example, circular hubs in order to establish **circular clusters** built on industrial symbiosis.
14. **Contact and learn from circular pioneers and champions:** In all structural changes, the speed of design and policy implementation is different. Learning from first movers is necessary for avoiding mistakes.

15. Communicate on circular progress based on monitoring: Actions that are not communicated do not exist. At this respect, it is important to monitor all actions, but even more important is to communicate progress levels. Monitoring and reporting on circular progress enable us to modify or intensify efforts depending on level of objective achievement.

Both approaches are converging in different ways and show a more or less detailed steps for transitioning and implementing circular economy either in cities or countries. In fact, our approach contains similar stages but grouped in an easier way and it is aligned with EIB and the Collaborating Centre on Sustainable Consumption and Production (CSCP) papers. As a result, applying circular economy in cities has important benefits, such as **reducing carbon emissions, improving liveability, increasing employment opportunities, health benefits and, consequently, contributing to climate action, resilience and economic recovery** in the post COVID-19.

Digitalisation is seen as one of the enablers of the Circular Economy due to its capacity of incorporate **visibility and intelligence in products and assets** such as, for example, knowledge of the location or condition and availability of assets. Increasing use of digital technologies such as artificial intelligence or blockchain technology allow the improvement of traceability and transparency throughout product lifetime. Concerning the necessary link between **circular economy and digital technologies**, Okorie *et al.* (2018) highlight that research fusing both areas has not been extensively explored. Interconnections between Industry 4.0 and data are suggested as leading role in enabling and scaling circular economy. Basically, this process uses some technologies and resources in industry as well as the same technologies are used for smart cities. We find digital circular economy linked to SDG12 Sustainable consumption and production and smart circular cities for achieving SDG15 too. Then, the objective is to **integrate digital technologies** (cloud, internet of things, additive manufacturing, big data and data analytics ...) and **circular economy objectives** either in industry or in cities.

More specifically, **digitalisation enables transparent access to data concerning products'** resource consumption and makes it possible to optimise product life cycles and thus promote the move towards the CE. In fact, basic challenges related to CE and digitalisation concern data ownership, **data collection, data sharing, data integration and data analysis that involve collaboration and competence requirements**. Different digital technologies use data, and this is the main input in the search of new solutions for circular economy. For this reason, we will focus on **data management in the digital technologies** in chapter 4. In relation with data sharing, gaining trust and security are grand challenges that can be tackled with innovative technological solutions, such as utilising blockchain (Antikainen *et al.*, 2018). Data Integration is another important issue, although ignored in some research of **digital circular solutions**.

Developing ideas about resolving circular challenges using data also requires **new business ideas** and, therefore, new business models that are related to finding **financing for the new business ideas**. In the next points, we introduce **business models and financing for circular economy projects** resulting from the different circular opportunities identified.

1.3. Business models in Circular Economy

To support the transition to the circular economy, circular modes of production, and the business models (BMs) that underpin them, play a crucial role. Results from the OECD Survey on the Circular Economy in Cities and Regions show that 85% of respondents consider the emergence of new BMs as a very relevant or relevant driver (OECD, 2020a).

At its core, the circular economy is about **creating new value chains** that decouple growth from the use of scarce resources through disruptive technology and business models based on the principles of circularity: **renewability, reuse, repair, upgrade, refurbishment, capacity sharing, dematerialization**, etc. (Lacy et al., 2020). To achieve this, requires companies to rethink the input side, transformation processes, and the output side of their BMs to capture value at every stage of the value chain (Lewandowski, 2016).

In this context, combining the challenges of placing CE into reality and BMs innovation leads to the concept of circular business models (CBMs), that has been identified as an important key for companies moving towards circular practices (Bocken et al., 2016). This section provides a brief overview of CBMs proposed in the literature, which will be further developed in task 4.3: Development of new business models for circularities which will be identified during Task 4.2 in the framework of WP4 of B-WaterSmart project.

A business model describes **how an organisation creates, delivers, and captures value** (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2010). Typically, linear business models are based on traditional “take, make, dispose” approach of production and consumption, using materials inefficiently, as their conservation is not considered. In contrast, CBMs redefine how companies create value while adhering to CE principles, keeping products and resources in circulation for as long as possible, preserving their embedded value, and, at end of use, cycling or looping them back into the system in **zero-waste value chains**. Therefore, CBMs differ from the traditional ones Figure 6 by concentrating on creating value for a broader range of stakeholders and taking into consideration also the benefits from societal and environmental perspectives (Antikainen et al., 2016).

Figure 6: Comparison of traditional and circular business models.
Source: Geissdoerfer et al. (2018)

There is no clear consensus in the literature on what is and is not a CBM. Based on literature, CBMs

can be defined as **business models that are cycling, extending, intensifying, and/or dematerialising material and energy loops** to reduce the resource inputs into and the waste and emission leakage out of an organisational system. This comprises recycling measures (cycling), use phase extensions (extending), a more intense use phase (intensifying), and the substitution of products by service and software solutions (dematerialising) (Geissdoerfer et al., 2020).

The literature on **circular business models** is growing fast and covers a variety of **different taxonomies** of models that vary in complexity and in the value proposition (Geissdoerfer et al., 2018). A review of this literature shows that some CBMs are frequently discussed, however, some classification approaches are slightly overlapping, and the distinction criteria is sometimes confused, using different wording to refer to similar CBMs (Lüdeke-Freund et al., 2018).

Some practitioner-oriented contributions that emerged in this literature are the **ReSOLVE** (Regenerate, Share, Optimize, Loop, Virtualize and Exchange) proposed by The Ellen MacArthur Foundation (EMF et al. 2015) or those developed by Accenture (Accenture 2014; Lacy et al. 2015,2020), where circular activities are categorised according to a business-centric perspective (OECD, 2019a).

To seize the opportunity value of redefining waste, Accenture present five CBMs that cover the full value chain of circularity (Lacy et al., 2020):

- **Circular Inputs:** Provides fully renewable, recyclable or bio-based resource inputs, replacing traditional single-lifecycle inputs in the supply chain.
- **Sharing Platform:** The utilization rates of products and assets are optimized through shared ownership, access, and usage typically enabled by digital technologies.
- **Product as a Service:** Offer product access and retain ownership to internalise benefits of circular resource productivity.
- **Product Use Extension:** Extend working lifecycle of products and components through design considerations, repairs, component reconditioning, upgrades, and resale on secondary markets.
- **Resource Recovery:** The value of embedded materials or energy from agricultural and industrial goods is captured through collection, aggregation, and processing at the end of a product's use through recycling, upcycling or downcycling.

These BMs are not mutually exclusive but complementary, as they can be used individually or in combination. For example, Desso, a carpet manufacturer, combines **Resource Recovery and Product as a Service**, applying Cradle to Cradle principles to design products that are planned to be taken back and recycled under a leasing agreement. In addition, **not all these business models are necessarily new** (e.g., the resource recovery business model has operated for millennia in the metal sector or the product as a service model is not so different from traditional product leasing), what is new is the growing diversity and sophistication of these business models, as well as the range of sectors in which they are adopted. For their adoption, consumer engagement, design, reverse logistics, disruptive technologies and ecosystems are five key enablers that are critical (Lacy et al. 2015, 2020).

In chapter 4, in order to propose CBMs and develop new ones to ensure the feasibility of each circular opportunity detected in each LL, several variables will be considered: value proposition, backstage elements (cost structure and key partners, activities and resources) and front stage elements (revenue streams and customer relationships, segments and channels).

2. The water circular economy in cities and regions

2.1. Circular Economy strategy through water concept

Circular Economy is a general strategy that needs to be implemented in each sector in order to generate all possible value. In fact, a circular economy comes from **natural systems and its base lies in system-thinking**. Water in the environment follows a natural circular model that secures water resources by regulating water flow and ensuring water quality. However, in human-managed systems that follow a linear model of **economic growth, water is successively qualitatively degraded after use**, becoming unfit for further use both by humans and ecosystems (Stuchtey, 2015). Renewable resources should be used wherever possible, natural systems are preserved or enhanced, waste and negative impacts are designed out. Materials, water, products and components are managed in loops, maintaining them at their highest possible intrinsic value. Application of circular economy principles will require **mapping the interactions of the water cycle**, how it is used, and where within the river basin or other water bodies (lakes, aquifers, groundwater and, of course rivers) and urban water cycles (including all water bodies) value can be extracted and new enterprises established. Accordingly, the incorporation of the **principles of circular economy and smart solutions** will allow to incorporate a smart sustainable management in water systems. Water needs to be preserved but beyond this, water is transporting materials and energy. The obvious link between water and **circular economy comes from wastewater**. From wastewater treatment plants, it is possible to **recover resources and materials as nutrients, organic matter, bioplastics etc, energy and sludge for agriculture**.

At this respect, a **white paper** with a more holistic vision is the result of a project between **ARUP**, Antea Group and Ellen MacArthur Foundation about **water and CE**. It lays the foundations for the CE approach in water systems that includes previous work done by IWA (2015) and Stuchtey (2015). ARUP et al., (2019), exploring links between water and CE that can be used to identify opportunities for application of CE principles to water systems. Is important to note that at many stages in the water cycle, from abstraction to treatment, distribution to discharge, a circular approach reveals opportunities for all stakeholders, including water utility companies, in particular to **conserve water, capture and re-use energy, extract and reuse valuable materials and by-products**, and, crucially, improve commercial operations. Switching from our existing, largely unsustainable, linear model of 'take, make, use, dispose' to a circular paradigm requires rethinking many aspects of production. The systemic nature of the circular economy requires both the ecosystem of water management and its individual components to change.

The diagram of Ellen MacArthur Foundation (see Figure 2) doesn't fit well with water systems because the origin was conceived from materials point of view. Water approach is based on the materials system diagram presented above but changing biological side for nature managed and technical side for human managed. The nature managed side represents the water cycle in a basin: from freshwater source to outflows without human intervention (not just the environmental concerns but also the risks for public Health). In this case, the natural **water cycle is doing re-optimisation, reusing and replenishment actions in the water bodies** (Figure 7).

Figure 7: Water System under Circular Economy thinking.

Source: ARUP, antegroup and Ellen MacArthur Foundation (2019) (collaborative project).

In the right side or Human Managed System, the natural system that is circular, per se, is altered by human management in three areas as **abstracting water, manipulating water loss in terms of acceleration and polluting water**. Then, it is possible to manage water incorporating the basic principle of **avoiding and reducing use, reusing water, recycling and replenishing water**.

Three CE principles were developed and adapted to sustainable water management – i.e., **Regenerate Natural Capital, Keep Resources in Use, and Designing out Waste Externalities** – in an effort to create a common basis for the development of a CE framework for water. The “Regenerate Natural Capital” principle (Figure 8) aims to ensure functional environmental flows and quantities, the “Keep Resources in Use” principle focuses on closing the resource loops, and the “Design Out Waste Externalities” principle targets the economically efficient reduction of waste (Nika et al., 2020).

Figure 8: Principles for systems interfacing with water.

Source: Arup et al. (2019), page 6.

However, it is important to include **other dimensions of water**, in other words, **water transports nutrients, chemicals and minerals and is a source of energy in order to broaden the strategy** due to the **links with energy, agriculture, industry, food production, waste and environment in the cities**. For this reason, it is necessary to think on multi-sectoral water CE approaches based on economic and environmental sectors and using and managing different resources. As CE is based on changes in production and consumption, the application of circular economy in water and its implementation need to consider the relationship with energy, industry, agriculture, waste and the environment. For this reason, any agenda should incorporate this holistic vision in addition to the own water system agenda.

In this sense, **Figure 9** incorporates all these relationships and illustrates the CE in the water sector.

Figure 9: Multi-sectoral process diagram illustrating the interdependencies between the different sectors and the natural environment in terms of water and other resources.

Source: Nika et al. (2020)

This holistic sectoral vision for achieving a more circular water sector should rely on **water systemic innovation** (Water Europe, 2016). Related to the first element, the water sector is already using smart data solutions in the value-chain, as well as other utilities, such as energy or transportation. Digital technology goes in hand with the named cyberinfrastructures, consisting of data collection systems (sensors and instrumentation), data storage systems, local and cloud-based computing systems, and data visualisation environments. These elements are all interconnected through software and networks, which improve data utilisation and, ultimately, allow us to better manage a wide range of societal challenges.

Moreover, developments in Artificial Intelligence, machine learning methods, robotics, virtual/augmented reality and serious games will foster the development of new insights into water management. At the same time, data should be available in order to increase public participation in water management decisions, while stimulating citizen engagement and understanding of water utility challenges. It is important in this point to remark the importance to protect and secure the data from cyber-attacks on infrastructure and terror entities. At this respect, The International Water Association⁶

⁶ The IWA Digital Water Programme was launched in 2019 and provides a platform for water utilities to explore and share experience on their digital water implementation. It includes a white paper series and a digital water report.

has a digital water programme and steps towards smart water are gaining positions. The Digital Water Report from IWA defines digital water as data, technologies and practices that drive value across the water and wastewater utility value chain, including customer engagement and water supply and water providers (IWA, 2019).

Nevertheless, smart solutions are less implemented for water circular economy. This is an important issue, and how to transition to a digital circular economy and specifically to a water digital circular economy is challenging. In fact, the link between circular economy and digital technologies is not yet well defined and research is being done in order to fill this gap as, for example, by Hedberg et al. (2019). In any case, smart circular economy should be supported by the creation, extraction, processing and sharing data from Digital Technologies (Kristoffersen et al., 2020).

As a result, digital technologies for circular water are at the beginning of the journey. There are advances in parallel and now crossing them is compulsory.

2.2. What to do? Towards a circular model in cities through water, energy and waste flow analysis

Although there is not a common strategy, we have designed a framework for implementing circular economy (figure 19) in cities and having in mind the holistic approach that includes **water, energy, agriculture, waste and ecosystems**.

Our approach intends to go beyond the works performed by Circular Economy framework promoting the Circular Economy concept at regional level through **defining, using and validating circular data for designing a strategy** to accelerate the transition towards circular economy in cities. This kind of approach presents the challenge of managing and analysing all the **substantial water-energy-waste data collected from the different key actors**. For this reason, we think that promoting the development of **circular economy digital** tools to support big data intake, visualization and analytics should be a good solution. Upon several use cases experiences we identify the need of a tool as a key factor for scaling up the methodology for **identifying circular economy opportunities** in a city.

The framework in Circular Economy from Ellen MacArthur Foundation is more convenient for businesses but presents some problems when applied to circular cities (Williams, 2019). In B-WaterSmart, we develop a **holistic methodology for implementing a regional Circular Economy Model** considering an input-output flow analysis (in terms of water, energy and waste) of regional key actors. In this line, the strategy should identify sectors that have potential for circular economy. Main sectors are waste, built environment, land use and spatial planning, food and water (OECD, 2020). From the water perspective, strategy should focus on the sectors with strong linkages with water, in other words, we will concentrate **in water, energy, waste and food**. This analysis should be conducted from an economic, environmental, social and governance perspective in order **to map all key actors (public or private)** in a city or region which should be involved to move towards to a circular economy model. These actors include the **city council, utilities (water, waste, energy, others), industries and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), citizens, natural areas managers, farmers, and other supra-administrations with competences at regional level** (Public administrations that offer an activity/be part of several closed municipalities), **among others** (for instance national regulators or others).

Based on limiting the scope to these sectors, next step relies on identifying the **regional/local actors who play a territorial role in cities**.

Challenges related to data are considered important. Ensuring access to data and questions related to data ownership are crucial. Sharing data is necessary in order to **perform a flow analysis**. Integration of big data owned by multiple actors and management of information flows is a relevant issue.

Then, the result must describe step by step how to **detect and map opportunities** of circularity from water, energy, waste and resources, linking inputs and outputs from each regional key actor, according to the administrative framework, and will set the basis for its evaluation and prioritisation.

Setting a roadmap is the next phase that includes milestones, potential barriers, potential economic, environmental and social impacts. Finally, **implementation issues as possible business models, way of governance and ways of funding** are included.

Once we have a strategic roadmap, the next phase is **the prioritisation and implementation of circular economy opportunities under an action plan**. Opportunities are reclaiming water for municipal or industrial purposes, a shared energy local manager for companies, eco-designed infrastructures or fiscal local incentives, for example (Termes et al., 2019). Finally, **monitoring and quantifying** impacts of different measures is done through different circular indicators.

Nevertheless, one of the key challenges is **data gathering, management and analysis**. Data on water, energy and waste comes from different actors and sources and in different formats, aggregation level, time horizons and periodicity. The greater the number of actors that can be involved and amount of data gathered and analysed, the greater the number of circular opportunities that can be identified. This Deliverable 4.2. will define a list of the CE indicators that allows the B-WaterSmart project to **measure the circularity assessment of opportunities that will be identified in each LL**. Although the development of measurement frameworks for circular economy is still incipient, some common obstacles and challenges can be observed, according to the OECD (2020):

- **An agreed definition of the circular economy**

It is important to understand and define what to measure, the reasons for doing it and the target audience before establishing an indicator framework. In the context of **Circular Economy International standard CTN323** where Cetaqua is participating in representation of Spain, Working Group 1 is working on the standard definition about circular economy.

- **Harmonisation of circular indicators**

There is no harmonised measurement framework contributing to a deeper understanding of the circular economy and its evaluation over time (Blomsma and Brennan, 2017). The existence of a broad variety of indicators makes it difficult to assess the robustness and reliability of the information provided (OECD, 2020). There is a lack of a sufficiently elaborated and consensual methodology for the monitoring and evaluation of the processes of the circular economy. However, in the context of Circular Economy International standard CTN323, where Cetaqua is participating in representation of Spain, working group 3 is elaborating the taxonomy scheme of water-energy-materials-waste nexus and a list of indicators. Also, the available indicators are mostly data-driven rather than objective-driven. Several monitoring frameworks are marked by data availability, resulting in some cases in an over-representation of sectors with greater availability of information (e.g., waste-related indicators). In the context of B-WaterSmart, D4.2 will collect the **definition of suitable circular indicators** to measure

the circularity in the 6 Living Labs, and in general for replication phase in others Living Labs/cities.

- **Integration at the macro-micro-meso levels**

The lack of integration between the macro-/micro-meso levels entails the risk of leading to conflicting strategies (Ekins et al., 2019). There is a need to link indicators from different levels, as it is currently not clear how to connect them.

- **Focus on closing loops**

*There is a strong focus on waste but little on **closing loops**.* Most indicator systems are focused on recycling and collection rates as well as on the 3R (Reduce, Reuse and Recycle) or the 9R (Rethink, Refuse, Reduce, Reuse, Re-gift, Repair, Rent, Recycle & Rot) (Saidani et al., 2019). Some of the indicators used to measure circularity (e.g., waste collection and recycling rate) may give a misleading indication of progress, as they do not necessarily show how the primary consumption of materials is reduced and optimised (Haupt, Vadenbo and Hellweg, 2017).

- **Product use analysis**

Existing indicators focus mainly on physical characteristics such as design, production and waste management, **lacking the analysis of the use of products**. Generally, indicators do not focus on the intelligent use of goods (addressing relevant factors such as planned obsolescence and ease of repair); instead, they report on the production and wasted resources.

- **Systemic approach of the circular economy indicators**

In order to move towards a system change, it is necessary for indicators to measure and control several factors (e.g., from urban planning to materials consumption) and not be limited to very specific sectors such as waste management (OECD, 2020).

As such, when **developing a circular economy strategy**, it is important to take into account the co-ordination across municipal and regional departments, the involvement of stakeholders for an inclusive and participative process, select several projects for the achievement of established targets and identify sources of funding. Communities of Practices or **Living Labs are articulators between different actors to take off the circularity in that regions**. The first step during Task 4.2 will be to define the technical questionnaires of data acquisition that we will need from each Living Lab (as we mentioned before, general information will be collected regularly through a data collection questionnaire in Milestone 5 of B-WaterSmart project) according with the data detailed in chapter 4 of this deliverable.

3. Circular Economy in the 6 Living Labs and their regions

Just to introduce the circular economy application in the context of B-WaterSmart, the WP4 team members completed a word cloud exercise to identify the **keywords concerning circular economy** and the result is summarized in the next figure:

Figure 10: Keywords associated with the circular economy.

Source: Own elaboration with WP4 team members.

Concepts as **climate, green, circular and sustainable** are linked to the **circular economy strategies** in most cities and regions. In some regions, the circular economy is included in the sustainability policy plan of the cities, or in the **Carbon-neutral 2030 Actions Plans**. In other regions, the circular economy is a means to achieve the city's goal to be fossil-free, while enhancing innovation and creating **the enabling environment for new business models**. Transitioning towards a circular economy has been a political priority for cities in the framework of strategic plans, setting the objectives for the cities to become **circular economy leaders**, developed an overall vision based on other key issues like public procurement, climate adaptation, waste and consumption. In addition, circular-related objectives in cities are included in green growth and regional development agendas. For example, some regions have adopted the **cross-cutting Policy Paper Vision 2050** including in one of their structural policies actions towards the circular economy; others have launched the **Climate and Energy Strategy**, which includes the circular economy as one of the focus areas and others circular strategies conceives the circular economy as an opportunity to achieve **sustainable goals at the regional level and as a key element of the Green Economy** based on policy coherence and **climate-related initiatives**.

The following section explains the **circular economy initiatives and characterizations** for 6 B-WaterSmart regions: **Alicante, Bodø, East Frisia, Flanders, Lisbon, Venice**. Several governments at various levels have been establishing a circular economy long-term vision. These have taken various forms such as: strategies (Spain); roadmaps (Belgium, Germany); action plans (Portugal), frameworks

(Italy), and white papers (Norway). The common point across national, **regional or local initiatives** is the long-term view, expressed in some cases through specific targets (OECD, 2020). Some of these territories are cities and regions that have already developed strategies or roadmaps and engaged a variety of stakeholders, others are “in progress”, thus are currently acting towards the circular economy, while others are starting the implementation. The benefits of implementing a circular economy are diverse and may differ for different actors, e.g. cities see in the circular economy a means for reducing environmental impacts while **increasing attractiveness** and competitiveness. Across the EU, and as represented by the 6 LLs, governments are gradually approaching the development and implementation of long-term strategies for a circular economy. As such, understanding **how roles and responsibilities for designing, financing, implementing and monitoring circular economy** initiatives are allocated across national, regional and local governments can help identify potential gaps and suggest effective ways forward towards the circular transition (OECD, 2020).

Following sections, explain the characterization of Living Labs that WP4 has collected from the two workshops in with the consortium (Workshop 1 on October 22nd and Workshop 2 on November 5th organised to define the water smart concept and framework and the characterization of Living Labs according to the socioeconomic, governance and technical water-energy-waste sources) and also have been updated by LL owners (section 3.1), preliminary stakeholders and their circular maps connections in each Living Labs are defined in section 3.2. In order to understand the circular economy initiatives, in each region and to be in consideration during the identification of circularities during Task 4.2. a list of circular economy initiatives according to region and for water-energy-waste fluxes have been added in Supplementary Information of Deliverable 4.1.

3.1. Characterization of Living Labs

Previous workshops helped WP4 to characterize the 6 Living Labs to define the scenarios for applying the circular economy value chains in the context of water-smartness. Some categories as key challenges, key solutions, water-energy-waste nexus, systemic innovation on water smartness and CE ongoing projects that will be very useful to start with the circularities in each Living Lab. Other data collected from these workshops will be developed further in other public Deliverables as 5.1. “Manual on stakeholder mapping and engagement” and 5.3 – Report “Drivers and Barriers for Water-Smart Solutions Across 6 European Cases: Policy and Governance” in Work Package 5.

Table 1 shows the main categories of information relevant for WP4 circular economy value chains and WP5 regarding data and information of governance and socio-economic aspects collected from Living Labs.

Table 1: Data collected through Workshop 1 and Workshop 2 elaborated within WP4 and WP5.

Source: Cetaqua own elaboration with the information provided by the LL owners.

Category	Definition of subcategories
1. Environmental conditions/indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1.1. Water sources (capacity, location, uses) 1.1.2. Water-energy-resource-waste nexus 1.1.3. Key environmental pressures (e.g. sea level rise, salinization, storm water and floods)
2. Socio-economic aspects/issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2.1. Population and scale 2.2. Social issues (Risk perceptions, possible social barriers) 2.3. Key water uses (Industrial, Urban, Agriculture, Reuse) - main socio-economic sectors, conflicting uses/demands 2.4. Economic barriers & drivers 2.5. Surveys (Available surveys on social and economic drivers of water management)
3. Systemic Innovation on Water Smartness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 3.1. LL WS Solutions 3.2. CE ongoing projects (Former and ongoing projects/initiatives relevant for water-smartness and circular economy) 3.3. Expected impact of B-WaterSmart 3.4. After the B-WaterSmart Project
4. Policy & Regulation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 4.1. Key policy instruments in relation to specific LL challenges 4.2. Policy gaps & trends 4.3. Regulation gaps & needs 4.4. Water-waste-energy nexus 4.5. Regulation system 4.6. COVID implications (e.g. water & quality & risk perceptions)
5. Governance system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 5.1. Decision-making levels - Institutions involved in water management, distribution and monitoring (across national, regional and local scales), as well as their main responsibilities 5.2. Operators responsible for water management in key economic sectors 5.3. Operators in water supply and distribution systems 5.4. Conflicts and tensions 5.5. Key stakeholders 5.6. Commitment (established agreements for long-term continuity of CE initiatives) 5.7. Co-design and co-management 5.8. Existent water culture (acceptance of water-related innovations) 5.9. Public engagement (participatory mechanisms & procedures)

3.1.1. Living Lab Alicante

Data characterisation of Alicante is defined in Table 2.

Table 2: Data collected from Alicante LL through Workshop 1 and Workshop 2 elaborated within WP4 and WP5.

Source: Cetaqua own elaboration with the information provided by the Living Lab Alicante.

Category	Definition of subcategories
Key challenges	<p>Alicante and its metropolitan area (1125 km²) are facing water scarcity challenges. Water scarcity, lack of local water resources and limitations to water reuse due to high salinity are the main challenges to face; there is a need to reuse 100% of the water regeneration capacity and to alleviate pressure on agricultural and municipal uses of potable water. This requires infrastructure investments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase agriculture reuse • Reduce the environmental impact of wastewater treatment • Address industrial reuse • Supply every green area of Alicante by expanding the double network • Create a Regional Reclaimed Water Network • Tackle the problem of wastewater salinization to improve reclaimed water quality and reduce treatment cost. • The main problems associated to agriculture water reuse (and to some extent, to other applications) are: Water salinity, demand/availability decoupling (seasonality), energy and infrastructure costs for reclaimed water transport
Key solutions	<p>To turn a wastewater treatment plant into a biofactory: recover minerals, nutrients & salts, energy; demonstrate a smart water allocation & negotiation tool to boost water reuse at municipality level.</p> <p>Identify key actions and investments to boost water reuse, involving stakeholders in the process</p>
Water- Energy- Material fluxes	<p>Water reuse is still limited, mainly due to its excessive salinity. Rincón de León Wastewater Treatment Plant (WWTP) (33,000 m³/day) includes a brackish water desalination plant based on ultrafiltration and reverse osmosis. Currently, 25% of regenerated water cannot be reused due to RO technical limitations. In terms of water volume, agriculture use is much more important; urban reuse is significant for its extent in terms of percentage of water use (for legally approved uses)</p> <p>Drinking Water: Groundwater wells providing water to Alicante are very deep (200-400 m) and thus water extraction consumes a lot of energy. Optimization of pumping is a priority; this objective has been reached to a great extent in the last decade, developing some innovative technical solutions.</p> <p>Agricultural users are concerned with water salinity, a technical barrier in providing water of quality. Desalination of reused water has a significant energy cost. Availability-demand decoupling for agriculture application due to seasonality is also a problem for water reuse.</p> <p>There are some concerns in relation to the return of unused treated water to the receiving body (Mediterranean Sea) as there are protected areas nearby. 20-25% sludge goes to</p>

<p>Systemic innovation on water smartness</p>	<p>agriculture (as fertilizer). Some ongoing research projects about advanced fertilizers production in collaboration with the local university. Most of the sludge to the cement industry (dried with waste heat from the plant, burned then in the plant as fuel). Some cogeneration systems installed, but room to improve through an increase of biogas production. The goal is to avoid greenhouse gas emissions as much as possible.</p> <p>Demonstration of 'hardware technologies' will mainly take place at the local level of a single WWTP (Rincón de León) with a full design capacity of 75.000 m³/day and serving 306.592 inhabitants:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increase of water reuse through EDR. - Recovery of materials / elements : NaClO production through Electrochlorination - Increase of energy production: codigestion + microturbines - Zero waste - Nutrient recovery: Ammonia recovery (ammonium salts production) + struvite production <p>Implementation of a neutral space for co-creation between the different stakeholders and ease access to citizens.</p>
<p>CE ongoing projects</p>	<p>The main application of reclaimed water is agriculture irrigation. The first private users of recycled water were golf courses, which still make use of this resource. Municipal irrigation of green areas has a growing importance, and it has been key for the improvement of the city environment (the extent of green areas has tripled thanks to the availability of reclaimed water). Presently, the company and the municipality successfully promote the access for small private customers. Special care has been devoted to avoid sanitary risks when dealing with this application (backflow prevention). No industrial use of reclaimed water until now.</p> <p>Other CE ongoing projects: initiative to recycle materials from city works, waste water sludge energy valorisation (see Water- Energy-Material fluxes)</p> <p>The ongoing European project NAIADES aims at reducing the waste water salinity problem at its source, by detecting, monitoring and locating infiltration points of saline water from the water table into the sewerage.</p>
<p>Policy & Regulation</p>	<p>Regulation gaps & needs: Regulation has been more focused on water quality, but there is also a need to encourage water reuse where necessary. Regulation for administrative concessions for water reuse is quite complex.</p> <p>The ministry for the ecological transition is responsible for every waste from the WWTP are reused, through directive 86/278/CE, either in agriculture or in sludge drying in CEMEX.</p> <p>Regulation system: Public organism in charge of providing water reuse permits and monitoring effluent and water body qualities: Cuenca Hydrographical del Júcar (CHJ). This is the river basin authority that regulates water in the basin where the treatment plant is located.</p> <p>Permits acquisition for 'hardware technologies' implementation will be managed by AMAEM, who is in constant collaboration with EPSAR (the regulator body in charge of</p>

Circular Economy impact in the B-WaterSmart project	<p>the wastewater treatment of the region). The project counts with a support letter from EPSAR indicating their commitment to allow the validation of the technologies proposed.</p>
	<p>CE in the territory is articulated partially through the Biofactories initiative fostered by the SUEZ Group for a number of operators in the Spanish territory. This approach will be complemented with the demonstration of innovative solutions for recovery of and CE-links for i) energy, ii) nutrients (nitrate and ammonia), iii) salt (chlorine generation from RO brine) and iv) mineral materials. The project will allow to boost a co-creation space (LL) where 'hardware technologies' and digital solutions will be demonstrated in order to unlock current existing barriers and ease better understanding of stakeholder's needs, as well as fostering negotiations.</p> <p>After the project end, AMAEM will seek to acquire additional capacity to operate the successful processes and tools at full-scale. Results will be replicated in/transferred to other operators of SUEZ Spain and SUEZ International. The multiplicity of techniques tested allows a tailored application to different plants. The conclusions of the decision support tools will be transferred to the municipal and regional infrastructure investment plans for implementation.</p>
Key stakeholders	<p>Alicante Municipality, EPSAR, Irrigation communities, University and Port of Alicante, Confederación Hidrográfica del Júcar. Industrial areas: Atalayas and Pla de Vallonga Relevant companies: Cemex, Helados Alacant, Suavinex, Famosa</p>

3.1.2. Living Lab Bodø

Data characterization of Bodø is defined in Table 3.

Table 3: Data collected from Bodø LL through Workshop 1 and Workshop 2 elaborated within WP4 and WP5.

Source: Cetaqua own elaboration with the information provided by Living Lab Bodø.

Category	Definition of subcategories
Key challenges	<p>Re-urbanization, increased pollution, growing resident population and economy, increased pollution, untapped efficiency potential. Focus Zero emission urban development to improve wastewater stream and air quality.</p> <p>Opportunity: Re-location of airport enables new sustainable city development. Calculate the available amount of surface water in Bodø in one year, and through a water balance model calculate the available volume at any given time.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Taking as starting point municipal consumption of water blue-green solutions and green infrastructure and mapping water needs against the available amount of surface water. - The right quality for the right use - what is required of the purification of surface water from various sources in relation to reuse, and then measured against the use of drinking water. This is measured with "water certificates" which indicate how sustainable and water-smart the solution is.

Key solutions	<p>Implementation of a small-scale biogas production; use heat from biogas and sea water for urban de-icing; smart system for advanced leakage & infiltration control.</p>
Water- Energy- Material fluxes	<p>Bodø has ample access on drinking water through good sources which require minimal water treatment.</p> <p>Remote areas use seawater and reverse osmosis treatment. Bodø's main water source is located 26 km from the city centre, but most of the distribution is automatic due to height difference. However, within the city water is distributed via pumps. In order to save energy an objective is to minimize production by minimizing water usage and leakages.</p> <p>Bodø is a partner in the centre for research-based innovation project ZEN (Zero emission neighborhoods) https://fmezen.no (2015-2023), where energy efficient and smart sustainable resource utilization are in focus, which gives a good starting point for B-WaterSmart pilot.</p> <p>Ongoing project to model the groundwater system. Bodø is a partner in the research CIRCULUS and City Loops. Both projects aim to reuse masses, both concrete from existing facilities at the military airport and general mass handling in a circular economy. Everything related to building the new district in a sustainable way. The source of drinking water for the city is well protected and far away, with natural fall, surrounded by mountain landscapes. It is a clean and good source with little pressure from human activity.</p>
Systemic innovation on water smartness	<p>Waste treatment plants - only primary plants, no secondary. A number of water meters have been installed in the municipality. The municipality has a master plan for water and sewage that is revised every four years. Directive shall contribute to the preservation, protection and improvement of water bodies and the aquatic environment and ensure the sustainable use of water resources. A number of directives have been laid down for the purpose of protecting water bodies. The Water Framework Directive forms a superstructure for all these directives. The directive covers all freshwater, groundwater and coastal water up to one nautical mile outside the baseline.</p> <p>The following environmental objectives apply to water bodies (coastal water, surface water and groundwater):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Achieve good chemical and ecological status in all water bodies. -Reduce the pollution load on watercourses and coastal waters. <p>These environmental goals can be seen in connection with various user interests such as better bathing water quality (where applicable) increased value for outdoor life, increased value for tourism, safer use of water for food purposes, increased biodiversity in rivers and coastal waters, safe seafood without risk of ingestion of environmental toxins, etc.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Strive for surface water from rivers and streams to be fed to the recipient either via natural open waterways or in separate pipes. -Consider assumed increased water volumes as a result of climate change when planning the surface water systems. -Contribute to the establishment of a financing scheme for surface water. -Have a renewal rate on the pipe network of 1% (measured as the length of the drainage network). -Separate discharges must be handled in accordance with the Pollution Control

	<p>Regulations. At the same time, there is a continuous assessment and improvement of the water systems. There is also systematic quality assurance of new facilities to capture leaks and avoid long-term and large leaks, by means of pressure testing.</p>
CE ongoing projects	<p>Solutions identified as positive must be implemented in the new district. For example, whether energy from treatment plants can be used to run buildings; or if water meters can be installed to have better control of water consumption; or if surface water and drain can be separated to minimise purification needs.</p>
Policy & Regulation	<p>Regulation gaps & needs: The pilots for technology #14 are all based on infrastructure owned by the city of Bodø (wastewater treatment plants and sludge management facilities).</p> <p>The leak detection coupled with smart water meter technology will be partly installed on infrastructure owned by the city and partly in private residences, requiring an agreement from the individual households. The district selection and stakeholder involvement will be run through the CoP in Bodø, and immediately initiated at the start of the project.</p> <p>Iris, the intermunicipal waste company in the region is responsible of sludge treatment.</p> <p>Regulation system: The Norwegian Food Safety Authority supervises the drinking water, the municipality itself has authority in the smaller cases, the county governor is responsible for the overall supervision of the municipality's work with the sewer network.</p>
Circular Economy impact in the B-WaterSmart project	<p>Expected B-WaterSmart project: Zero emission urban development, improved wastewater stream, improved air quality; work on three challenges characteristic for many small to medium size cities in northern regions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -improve resource recovery from wastewater in an efficient way given the small scale, especially concerning biogas production from sludge and aid in technology selection. -improving wastewater quality by developing better infiltration detection technologies, coupled with leak detection technologies, in an integrated system. Technology testing and selection to achieve both reduced energy consumption and improve the quality of the wastewater stream. -reducing the use of de-icing and anti-slip agents in the city centre to significantly improve air quality and reduce soil & water pollution. The alternative de-icing will use excess heat from biogas utilization for electricity production in combination with seawater. The project will build and test technology for use of seawater as a heat source in the city centre. The performance will be measured in terms of improved air quality and better energy efficiency of the system. <p>Impact after B-WaterSmart project: develop a plan for the new district using blue-green infrastructure with no non-potable use of drinking water, including first replication of the 'water-smart for climate-ready' building certificates developed and applied in Lisbon. Relocation of the airport and redevelopment of the airport area has already secured significant national funding. Redevelopment of the old airport area has high environmental and social ambitions, which are aligned with the ambitions of the B-WaterSmart project.</p>

List of stakeholders	<p>IRIS: intermunicipal waste company - compost of sewage sludge;</p> <p>Construction industry</p> <p>Technology companies/developers, Bodø Energi Varme AS, AVINOR, Norwegian Food Safety Authority (Drinking water); National Institute of Public Health, County governor (sewage)</p> <p>Stavenger Komune, Trondheim Kommune</p>
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3.1.3. Living Lab East Frisia

Data characterization of East Frisia is defined in Table 4.

Table 4: Data collected through Workshop 1 and Workshop 2 elaborated within WP4 and WP5. Source: Cetaqua own elaboration with the information provided by LL East Frisia.

Category	Definition of subcategories
Key challenges	<p>Increasing water demand by growing different sectors but limited resources; regional imbalances of water resources' availability</p> <p>Overall goal: Identify untapped water resources and increase reuse of process water and wastewater in water-demanding key industries</p> <p>Ambitions until project end:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pilot plant will be operated to test improved treatment of cow water for reuse in water-intense sector of dairy production. • Long-term water demand assessment (demands and analysis of available water resources). • Improvement of short-term water demand forecast via smart metering • Innovative approach to match available water qualities with required standards of different uses (e.g. industry, agriculture). • Know-how in water reuse technologies will be used to establish a new business model for OOWV. Expected Impact: Integrated water resource management within the whole OOWV supply area.
Key solutions	<p>Demonstrate reuse of treated process water as replacement of drinking water in dairy & food industry, tap urban groundwater as service water resource, improve water demand forecast via smart metering</p>
Water- Energy- Material fluxes	<p>Currently groundwater represents 100% of the supply being a partly remote water supply. Untapped resources: seawater, brackish water, drainage water, process water, local process water streams, wastewater, surface water</p> <p>Water resources within the catchment area are limited, increasing peak load in waterworks during heat summers; recent ground water protection strategies involve extensive agricultural consultation in selected areas on a voluntary basis; model-based forecast of available water quality and quantity under conditions of climate change.</p>

<p>Systemic innovation on water smartness</p>	<p>LL WS solutions: Develop a sectional decentralized water supply strategy using untapped local water resources, e.g. reuse of treated process water instead of drinking water in dairy & food industry, e.g. wastewater reuse for other industries, tap urban groundwater as service water resource, improve water demand forecast via smart metering, rainwater management.</p>
<p>CE ongoing projects</p>	<p>MultiReUse - Modular treatment and monitoring for wastewater reuse: Development, demonstration and evaluation of a modular treatment system with central and decentralized elements for industrial, commercial and agricultural use, including a pilot plant in Nordenham.</p> <p>INTERREG AQUARES- Water reuses policies advancements for resource efficient European regions: Efficient water management through water reuse, developing strategies, making optimal use of EU funding elements and public dialogue.</p> <p>KENOW project: use of sludge from wastewater treatment plants to produce energy; thermal sewage sludge recycling (EWE, SWB, OOWV, HVE).</p>
<p>Policy & Regulation</p>	<p>Regulation gaps & needs: German drinking water ordinance</p> <p>Regulation system: Federal or regional environment agency</p>
<p>Circular Economy impact in the B-WaterSmart project</p>	<p>Expected B-WaterSmart impact: Increase resilience of water supply: i) exploration of alternative resources, ii) smart protection strategies of groundwater bodies based on in-situ circulation; iii) improved treatment of vapour condensate and whey permeate for reuse in dairy production.</p> <p>OOWV aims to identify untapped water resources and increase reuse of process water and treated wastewater in water-demanding key industries to reduce groundwater abstraction. A pilot plant will be operated to test improved treatment of vapour condensate and whey permeate for reuse in water intense sector of dairy production. The task involves the test of a combined biology-UF-RO treatment of vapour condensate & milk/whey permeate for reuse in dairy industry, through a pilot treatment train (moving bed biofilm reactor - multi layer filter - ultrafiltration - reverse osmosis - UV disinfection) on a demonstration scale (6 m³/h) to assess the quantity and quality of reuse water (and residuals), as well as operational costs.</p> <p>Options for new digital solutions for monitoring will be evaluated. A high-resolution assessment will be performed for the supply area of OOWV to develop a quality-driven local water supply of selected industrial consumers. To deliver this, a GIS-based spatial multi-criteria approach (Regional Demand-Supply Matching GIS Tool) will be developed to identify water requirements and match these with regionally available water resources. Finally, the forecasting of domestic water demand will be improved, by placing smart meters within the OOWV supply area.</p> <p>Local recirculation strategies will be part of water-smart structures for the OOWV supply area. Feasibility studies will focus on i) the in-situ circulation of groundwater; and ii) the usability of alternative water resources for industrial purposes.</p> <p>The OOWV will be able to offer reused water and water from alternative resources "fit-for-purpose" for industrial uses including the food industry. This will be a new product</p>

	<p>that can substitute drinking water for industrial customers.</p> <p>Impact after B-WaterSmart project: An integrated water resource management including alternative resources and water reuse for non-potable uses will be established within the whole OOWV supply area by using the tools & methods developed within this project. OOWV will use the technical know-how in water reuse technologies to establish a new business case for the company. Water reuse plants and process-water recycling plants will be planned, construct and operated.</p>
<p>List of stakeholders</p>	<p>Company: EnviroChemie</p> <p>EnviroChemie is a leading plant engineering company for industrial water treatment, water circulation and wastewater treatment. Plant solutions include water recycling, resource recycling or zero discharge requirements. For B-WaterSmart, EnviroChemie will design, build and operate a pilot plant for water recycling within a dairy factory: The water that remains when dairy products are dried, the so-called cow water, will be treated with a combination of processes to achieve drinking water quality. This pilot plant will demonstrate within the living lab 'East Frisia' that such a water recycling plant produces hygienically save drinking water from cow water.</p> <p>Company: DKM Molkerei Edeweicht</p> <p>With around 7,700 employees at more than 20 locations in Germany, the Netherlands and other international hubs, Germany's largest dairy cooperative processes milk into food products of the highest quality. The product portfolio ranges from cheese, dairy products and ingredients to baby food, ice cream and whey products. It is priority for the DMK Group to ensure more sustainability along the entire value chain, use resources economically and implement holistic environmental protection in production and retailing. As part of B-WaterSmart DMK demonstrates the reuse of treated process water as a substitute for drinking water at the Living Lab in East Frisia.</p> <p>Company: INTWA</p> <p>Registered association founded in 1988. Members are water suppliers from Lower Saxony. The purpose of the association is the protection and long-term assurance of the quality and quantity of water for drinking water supply.</p>

3.1.4. Living Lab Flanders

Data characterization of Flanders is defined in Table 5.

Table 5: Data collected from Flanders LL through Workshop 1 and Workshop 2 elaborated within WP4 and WP5.

Source: Cetaqua own elaboration with the information provided by LL Flanders.

Category	Definition of subcategories
<p>Key challenges</p>	<p>High drinking water demand due to dense population, high irrigation water demand for agriculture, groundwater overexploitation, water quality deterioration, water scarcity due to droughts and climate change; dense population, intensive farming,</p>

	<p>groundwater overexploitation, quality deterioration, droughts. Integration of water systems, improvement water smartness, better monitoring of water smartness.</p>
<p>Key solutions</p>	<p>Establish regional circularity in the water system: include alternative water resources for water supply, secure irrigation by integration with urban reuse cycle; improve performance of existing drinking water system.</p>
<p>Water- Energy- Material fluxes</p>	<p>Water fluxes: surface water (for drinking water production), rainwater, run-off stormwater (for irrigation).</p> <p>De WaterGroep: current objective is to use as few raw materials as possible and valorise the waste they generate (e.g. the usage of iron sludge). With multi-stage RO, robustness of drinking water installation will be increased, but more energy will be used, and concentrate will be produced, a waste stream that requires attention. Energy production can be compensated with decentralised green energy sources, but the concentrate is a bottleneck.</p> <p>Belgium ranks 23rd globally in the 2019 National Water Stress Ranking and transforming the regional water system from linear to fully circular, integrating the urban and natural water cycles, is key for securing a freshwater supply for all sectors. Especially after the 2017 and 2018 droughts, there is strong interest to explore alternative water sources and work towards a more robust, water smart system. Longer periods of drought, higher concentrations of pesticides, contaminants and salts are new challenges that must be addressed.</p>
<p>Systemic innovation on water smartness</p>	<p>Regional scale: model development water system for Mechelen (86,600 inhabitants), and De Watergroep (3.3 million customers, 365,000 Mm³ drinking water/day).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstration on effluent reuse for drinking water (3 – 6 m³/h) will make use of tools and technologies. The results of this demonstration will help De Watergroep to decide on implementation of effluent as an additional drinking water source at production site Diksmuide, as well as other potential sites identified in the water system model. • Demonstration of improvement of De Watergroep installation by multi-stage RO to increase drinking water robustness for the region. • Demonstration Mechelen: stormwater reuse for irrigation (water volume 1000 m³ per storm event, at least 3 events expected, provides irrigation for ca. 30 ha of cropland) and will make use of tools). If successful, the irrigation system can be expanded to several other farms, and the concept transferred to other potential sites identified in the water system model.
<p>CE ongoing projects</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Several local implementations of alternative water sources are currently being explored by the case partners, including alternative water resources and ASR storage buffer for drinking water (De Watergroep), and stormwater retention and reuse for agriculture (Mechelen). • Irrigation / Infiltration in soil • Construction retention pond, buffering stormwater (managing the water in the basin, controlled outlet)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitoring water streams (catchments, groundwater, soil moisture real time water management system (modelling & software)) Monitoring water quality (food safety) Mobile unit: Heavy metals, biological (E.Coli)
<p>Policy & Regulation</p>	<p>Regulation gaps & needs: For the pilot at De Watergroep, permits needed depend on type and scale of purification system. For the planned demonstration no permit is required. A permit is required for subsurface storage.</p> <p>For Mechelen demonstration, permits are currently underway for the installation of the basin and irrigation system. As the city of Mechelen is partner of the project and the province has signed a letter of interest, no issues are expected.</p> <p>Development of the regional water system model and tools will be informed by the results from the demonstrations but can proceed independently. No permits are needed for tool development.</p> <p>Potential alternative demonstration cases are available at De Watergroep if the current demonstrations cannot proceed due to regulatory issues.</p> <p>Waste services (not-water) is a private market; energy production is also a private market.</p> <p>Regulation system: VMM is the Environment Agency of the region is responsible for regulation and permitting of environmental issues including (waste) water; they are also responsible for reporting of the state of the environment towards the EU (e.g. WFD).</p>
<p>Circular Economy impact in the B-WaterSmart project</p>	<p>Expected B-WaterSmart impact: Development of regional concept for improving and monitoring water-smartness and a more robust water system, with a focus on safe water reuse. Assess the regional water system and its potential for incorporation of water-smart solutions, close water cycles, increasing resilience and integrating the existing natural water system as a nature-based solution, while ensuring safe reuse. Water availability and demand including potential alternative water sources will be modelled using UWOT as Urban Water Optioneering Tool to develop a regional strategy to increase water system robustness. The QMRA+ tool will be developed to assess water reuse safety. Practical implementation of water reuse and production will be demonstrated on three sites (Diksmuide, Mechelen and De Blankaart) with high transferability potential for the region:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -effluent reuse for drinking water -urban stormwater reuse for irrigation -improvement of the existing drinking water production by multi-stage RO <p>Impact after B-WaterSmart project: The experiences from the demonstration sites will be used to identify the potential for valorisation of the applied technologies at a larger scale at those locations, as well as implementation at other locations in the regional water system identified in the regional water system model. The assessment of the regional water system for Mechelen and De Watergroep will enable systemic innovation in the region and form the basis of a roadmap for a systemic smart water management in Flanders in 2040.</p>

List of stakeholders	<p>The province or a local water body ('polders' and 'wateringen'): Polder management</p> <p>Organisations: Zuidijzerpolder, Westkustpolder for drinking water public companies (owned by municipalities) are responsible for water provision and distribution process water management and distribution is a private market; wastewater treatment management is done by municipality, companies at a local level, and by Aquafin at a regional level.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Horticulture: farmers and farmer unions, Agricultural sector (Boerenbond, Algemeen Boerensyndicaat (ABS); • Drinking water sector: Aquaflanders • Nature organization: Natuurpunt • VMM (Regulatory body)- env agency of Flanders City of Mechelen (project partner) Municipality of Diksmuide • Knowledge providers • Agriculture: Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt (PSKW)
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3.1.5. Living Lab Lisbon

Data characterization of Lisbon is defined in Table 6.

Table 6: Data collected from Lisbon LL through Workshop 1 and Workshop 2 elaborated within WP4 and WP5.

Source: Cetaqua own elaboration with the information provided by LL Lisbon.

Category	Definition of subcategories
Key challenges	<p>Growing resident population & economy, dependent on distant freshwater resources, climate change challenges, tourism, need to increase urban green areas.</p> <p>Development of water smart tools & processes to facilitate safe water reuse and improve water-energy-phosphorous efficiency.</p> <p>Managing water demands and enable efficient allocation of available water resources</p> <p>Improving Lisbon's climate readiness and resilience in particular, regarding water scarcity.</p>
Key solutions	<p>Optimise urban water-energy-P balance, portfolio of efficiency measures, planning & monitoring tools, a water observatory, smart metering at housing, 'water-smart for climate-ready' building certificates, increase green areas without more freshwater abstraction</p>
Water- Energy- Material fluxes	<p>Lisbon is supplied by 2 surface and 4 groundwater sources. The main source - Castelo do Bode reservoir, with a production capacity of around 625,000 m³ per day, represents 83% of water supplied for potable uses (54,79 Mm³/year).</p> <p>There are 3 WRRFs in Lisbon, which treat 48.57 million m³/year (Alcântara), 14.11 million m³/year (Beirolas) and 12.24 million m³/year (Chelas). Currently, the Lisbon municipality reuses over 1.55 million m³/year of wastewater produced in the 3 WWTP for their own internal non potable uses and public street cleaning.</p> <p>3 main axes of the Lisbon integrated strategy:</p> <p>1) Drinking water saving and water resilience: Building efficient water</p>

	<p>management; Public spaces efficient water management (closing the urban water cycle, Nature-Based solutions to retain and infiltrate water (microscale, natural, storm water management), dry fed and adapted plant cover, green space design and management, installation of smart meters to prevent and reduce losses.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2) Water alternative sources (including water reuse, risk assessment technology, public health safety and public acceptance). 3) Water-smart culture: developing water-energy nexus, requiring new business models, recommending new regulations for water reuse (CM Lisboa; AdTA) <p>Lisbon has no surface water bodies within the city limits. Growing resident population and economy, dependent on distant freshwater resources, climate challenges (e.g. droughts and floods), need to increase urban green areas; an increasing drought and scarcity risk in Portugal recommends a preventive drought management.</p> <p>-The national energy production and distributions is a private market. The production of energy in Portugal takes place through wind generation, through the company EDP Renováveis, and through hydro and thermal generation (coal, water and combined cycle of natural gas), through the company EDP Produção. The distribution of energy is managed by EDP Distribuição.</p> <p>-Grupo AdP – Águas de Portugal is the holding that owns the Lisbon’s water supply company EPAL and the wastewater company AdTA, has a self-energy efficiency plan PEPE (https://www.adp.pt/pt/sustentabilidade/boas-praticas/gestao-da-energia/?id=54).</p> <p>-Valorsul manages the urban waste and recycling of Lisbon.</p>
<p>CE Ongoing projects</p>	<p>Development of tools & processes to facilitate safe water reuse and improve water-energy phosphorous efficiency, improving Lisbon’s climate readiness regarding water scarcity; deliver algorithms and software for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -City water cycle components’ quantification and W-E-P balance assessment -Creating Lisbon’s urban water cycle observatory, an open source information platform to support public engagement, urban planning and decision making (open data for public, and reserved data sets to input into decision-making tools) -Risk assessment of alternative water sources (health risk approach based on ISO standards (whose recent development involved LNEC) and on EU regulation, greatly grounded on ISO standards; environmental risk based on surface and groundwater vulnerability). -Modelling reclaimed water quality in the distribution network to support the network’s design and management <p>Performance-cost-risk based decision support tool for W-E-P sustainable management. Water-smart tools tested at city level and with multiple users (municipality, agriculture, beer industry, tourism). Further, a protocol for food-grade water production from treated wastewater will be demonstrated for beer industry. A climate-readiness index will be validated in pilot households and buildings, and the subsequent auditing/certification mechanism for Climate Readiness will be delivered for municipal (and replicated to private) buildings, new or renovated ones. Other ambitions are to put in place a key mechanism of systemic innovation in Lisbon Living Lab, during and beyond the B-WaterSmart project to train Lisbon LL partners and stakeholders to use every B-WaterSmart product relevant for their current or foreseen specific context, and to</p>

	<p>build CML's capacity to use the water-smartness framework and dashboard.</p>
<p>Systemic innovation on water smartness</p>	<p>Lisbon's European Green Capital 2020 Award catalysed political willingness and investments to improve the city's water-smartness as a tool for adaptation to water scarcity tool and an enabler for sustainable increase of green areas:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Recent and forthcoming national & EU regulation calling for sound guidelines/tools for risk management -Lisbon's affordable housing programme -National plans for Circular Economy and carbon-neutrality <p>Currently, the 3 WRRF (Water Resource Recovery Facility) from Lisbon produce 72.400 ton/year of sludge, which are sent for composting and for later agricultural valorisation outside Lisbon. The Beirolas and Chelas WRRFs have anaerobic digestion of sludge and produce electricity from biogas for self-consumption (Beirolas 1.2 GWh/year and Chelas 1.6 GWh/year). The water produced in the 3 WRRFs is reused for internal uses (e.g. landscape irrigation, street/equipment cleaning, chemical preparation) and external uses (street cleaning).</p> <p>AdP Group, including AdTA, aims to be energy neutral by 2030. Alcântara and Beirolas WRRFs will have a capacity of 990 kW and 240kW with solar panels. This plan focuses on investment in solar, wind and biogas.</p>
<p>Policy & Regulation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Water reuse for urban irrigation and street washing (74% of municipal consumption) aims to further reduce potable water consumption but has been difficult due to inexistent regulation up to 2019 and highly restrictive licensing conditions since then. For instance, Parque Tejo pilot project is waiting for water reuse irrigation permit. Only one supply entity (EPAL) licensed in Lisbon, law needs be changed in order to allow other entities in the water supply system. Lisbon municipality at the moment has to use the reused water themselves but is not allowed to sell to others. -Implementation of water efficiency standards in municipal buildings but no auditing/certification mechanism is in place and no program for private buildings. -Positive recent changes: the new decree-law, approved in August for water reuse regulate quality standards for the water reuse licenses - production, distribution and application but implementation in practice has proven complex. <p>Regulation gaps & needs:</p> <p>Despite having the National Program for efficient use of water and the Strategic Plan for Water Supply and Wastewater 2020, a regulation on water business for water reuse is needed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Only some 2 licenses attributed in Portugal yet for production and application -Lisbon municipality has the first pilot project for irrigation of green areas/public parks (public areas with free access) that requires a license permit from APA – the Portuguese Environment Agency, which was already been requested for the specific pilot area (Parque Tejo). The demonstration activities of water reuse (risk assessment and water quality network modelling) are the most complex issues until now. Risk assessment has been a key limiting issue but B-WaterSmart working on risk assessment tools to make it easier.

<p>Circular Economy impact in the B-WaterSmart project</p>	<p>Expected B-WaterSmart impact:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -20% Decrease in use of freshwater resources (40% by 2040) -15% Improved water use efficiency (25% by 2040) -5% Water reuse/Water supplied (15% by 2040) -20% Reduction in water-related energy use -5% Nutrient recovery (P, 20% by 2040) <p>Impact after B-WaterSmart project: An innovative urban water cycle observatory construction, and new 'water-smart for climate-ready' building certificates and financing mechanisms for water efficiency and CE, which will boost the creation of new business opportunities. Risk assessment tools & operational procedures in place, which will facilitate adoption of water reuse by other cities in the region (neighbouring cities like Cascais and Torres Vedras are followers already engaged, and guidelines for tools and process implementation will be provided to all 18 municipalities of the Lisbon Metropolitan Area), supporting the development & implementation of the Portuguese and European related-policies and SDGs.</p>
<p>List of stakeholders</p>	<p>AEPSA (technology providers association), PPA (Portuguese Water Partnership)</p> <p>DECO (consumers association), APDA (association of water utilities), APESB (association of water professionals & utilities), APRH (association of water professionals & utilities), ZERO (environment NGO), GEOTA (environment NGO), QUERCUS (environment NGO), potential followers - all municipalities covered by the Lisbon metropolitan area and large non-potable consumers, Águas do Tejo Atlântico,</p> <p>EPAL- Water services Portugal, EDP- Private energy sector</p> <p>ValorSul- private waste company, APRH- association of water professionals & utilities, ANQIP-National Association for Quality in Built Environments, Developed an equipment certification for water efficiency), University, ERSAR- Water and waste regulatory, Metropolitan Area Lisbon</p> <p>Associated Municipality, CCDRCLVT- Regional Commission for Coordination and Development of Lisbon and Tagus Valley circular economy, APA- Portuguese Environmental Agency</p> <p>ERSE - Regulator Energy sector, Cascais Ambiente (Municipality of Cascais); Municipality of Torres Vedras; Metropolitan Area of Lisbon and its 18 municipalities.</p>

3.1.6. Living Lab Venice

Data characterization of Venice is defined in Table 7.

Table 7: Data collected from Venice LL through Workshop 1 and Workshop 2 elaborated within WP4 and WP5.

Source: Cetaqua own elaboration with the information provided by LL Venice.

Category	Definition of subcategories
<p>Key challenges</p>	<p>Limitations to reuse and recovery due to low acceptance, water scarcity, untapped efficiency potential (water and resources valorisation).</p> <p>Lack of objective knowledge on real risks and real benefits of the application of resource recovery and CE logics.</p> <p>Creation of stable conditions to complete the treated water reuse objectives envisaged by the PIF (Integrated Fusina Project), enhancing freshwater saving.</p> <p>Improve nitrogen recovery in concentrated streams of WWTPs, towards a circular economy and energy savings in the plant.</p> <p>Create an objective and circumstantial awareness, with a transferable evaluation system, to direct treated effluents and sewage sludge towards the most sustainable valorisation solutions.</p>
<p>Key solutions</p>	<p>To demonstrate the opportunity and convenience of water reuse, a compact pilot plant of combinatorial technologies to target wastewater reuse at industrial level will be implemented and applied to the effluent of the Fusina plant (PIF).</p> <p>New technologies and business models (involving competences for market and regulations) will be implemented to allow nutrient recovery from concentrated WWTPs streams and salt production.</p> <p>IT systems for integrated evaluations (IES) will be provided to: i) evaluate opportunity for extensive wastewater reuse at multiple level (industrial, urban, agricultural); ii) pursue nutrient/energy recovery from sewage sludge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For water, all issues and barriers (requirements and infrastructures needs, geographical, political and regulatory) will be treated in negotiation tables with all stakeholders to rank reuse opportunities for freshwater preservation. Standard criteria for shared evaluations and barriers mitigations will be integrated in the IT platform, transferable to other realities and EU regions. - For sludge the goal is to lead the different actors involved in the choices of treatments and technologies to be applied to sludge management. Technical/economic data, quality-quantitative balances, environmental, social and policy factors, will be taken into account and a rank of the solutions with the identification of optimum one will be given. The whole work will be made starting from evaluations related to our territory, by using for the ranking of sustainable reuse sequences at least 40% of the sludge produced at Regional level (around 200k tons/year).

<p>Water- Energy- Material fluxes</p>	<p>Ground and river water for drinking water production; freshwater from two rivers (Sile and Naviglio Brenta) currently used for industrial, urban and agricultural purposes.</p> <p>Three main areas of interests in the Venice case study:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Water: minimal fraction (1%) of Fusina treated wastewater (total around 40 Mm³/years) actually reused in the industrial site, the rest is discharged into the sea. - Nutrient: at WWTPs level, the ammonium nitrogen is actually not recovered as bio-resource but only biologically treated. There are some experiences of Ammonium Sulphate production from stripping of liquid waste (landfill leachate) from industries (Etra-Depuracque), but only in some cases the CE cycle is closed with market economic benefit for the salt producer. - Sludge: more than 40% of the total sludge produced in the Veneto Region is managed by Veritas and Etra. Its management represents great issues for utilities, which are often forced towards economic and environmental prohibitive solutions due to the lack of knowledge, strategic and coordinated vision, regulatory and societal pressures that do not support sludge direct or indirect reuse in agriculture. Some regulatory lack and ambiguities prevent from systematically undertaking the valorisation of sludge in agriculture. This is favoured also by the absence of clear regulations at European level, where each Country adopts its own strategies. <p>Energy aspects are not the main theme for the Venice case, but they represent essential elements for the economic evaluations of the different valorization/recovery opportunities and convenience for water, sludge (through the platforms) and nutrient.</p>
<p>Systemic innovation on water smartness</p>	<p>Enable and contribute to complete the water industrial reuse goal of a regional/national plan for lagoon protection (PIF), by evaluating also the opportunity of other kind of resource reuses (agricultural and urban) through the development of an objective support for the decision system (platform). Apply nutrient recovery technologies to WWTPs and develop shared evaluation model-tools for the sustainability of WWTP effluents and sludge valorisation.</p> <p>The sharing and spreading of scientific and objective knowledge, especially through the development of decision support platforms, will allow to carry out stable and objective evaluations and better identify the risk and real benefits associated to the RR-CE application; that will lead to the unlocking of CE practices.</p>
<p>CE ongoing projects</p>	<p>Production of ammonium sulphate, from stripping of liquid waste (Landfill leachate or other), sold as product for industrial/agricultural sectors or recovered to balance nutrients in biological treatments for industrial WW.</p> <p>A specific research area from Gruppo Veritas S.p.A. is currently investigating alternative energies (biogas, biomethane, biofuels, etc.) from renewable resources (waste, biogas, algae and other sources also produced in WWTPs).</p> <p>Several examples/studies for biogas/biomethane production from anaerobic co-digestion of sludge and Organic Fraction of Municipal Solid Waste (OFMSW), that allows to recover energy used for the WWTPs self-sustenance.</p>

	<p>Studies and pilot/industrial scale plants projects on biopolymers (e.g. PHA, polyhydroxyalkanoates) production from co-digestion of sludge and OFMSW.</p> <p>Several studies, projects and initiatives on efficient resource recovery and closing the loop of productive cycles from wastewater treatment to recover materials (e.g. cellulose, biopolymers, struvite, etc.).</p>
Policy & Regulation	<p>Regulation gaps & needs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Water: A regional/national plan for the lagoon protection (PIF) allowed to introduce technologies, even Nature Based Solutions, to foster the reuse of treated municipal wastewater at industrial level, but several factors (such as industrial recession) and barriers (such as lack of sharing and integration among the several competences and roles) have delayed some goals. Moreover, to pursue water reuse objectives also at agricultural level, there is the concern of the National Law (185/2003) which is very restrictive and complex to comply with. - Nutrient: Regulation for product and secondary product recovery/selling is complex, not clear and not stable, with slow and uncertain authorization processes. Public producers are forced to precautionary classify the product inside the waste legislation to avoid the risk to be exposed. - Sludge: Lack of clear regulation to promote the reuse/recovery of sludge. In Italy the limits foreseen for reclaimed lands have been wrongly applied to sludge application on soils; moreover, sewage sludge is the "great excluded" from the "End of Waste" regulation for fertilizers and compost and from the Circular Economy European packages. <p>Regulation system:</p> <p>National scale: The Parliament defines the general regulations (National Law and EU directive implementation). The ISS (Superior Institute of Health) act as a consultant for the protection of public health.</p> <p>Regional and Local Scale: the Veneto Region is the main administrative division of the Region, responsible for the National Law contextualization's in the territory (with some margin of modifications only if more restrictive) and for some Authoritative procedures (particular discharges in the environment) or treatment/plant significant upgrade and new Plant designing). The Metropolitan City of Venice (provincial level) is the Local Public administrative Authority for the integrated environmental management and pollution control. It manages some Authoritative procedures for treatment plants and discharges</p>
Circular Economy impact in the B-WaterSmart project	<p>Expected B-WaterSmart impact:</p> <p>The water services provider (Veritas) aims at mitigating/removing barriers, while demonstrating the opportunity and sustainability of RR and CE logics.</p> <p>For freshwater savings and wastewater reuse, the organization of specific and stable working tables to find the convergence points and adopt standard criteria to evaluate convenience and foster WWR at multiple level will allow to mitigate barriers. The sustainability (environmental and economic) of the proposed solution, compared to the existing treatment sequence applied to river freshwater, will be evaluated. All variables and factors contributing, to achieving reuse (requirements and infrastructures needs, geographical, political and regulatory issues) will be considered to evaluate reuse opportunities.</p>

	<p>All the information and variables appropriately combined and declined will be integrated in the developed IT platform for water resources and digital solutions (WRSP for DSS), to make transferable to other realities and EU regions the standardized model of assessment to mitigate barriers.</p> <p>At nutrient recovery level, best practices in the wastewater treatment to recover N will be fostered. Solutions to provide the produced salt to industrial/agricultural final users will be individuated. To this purpose, two different stripping technologies will be implemented on WWTP digestion eluates and compared to individuate the most convenient from a technical and economic point of view.</p> <p>Impact after B-WaterSmart project</p> <p>Achieving as much as possible the extensive reuse of the treated municipal wastewater, by upscaling the demonstrated pilot technology at industrial level and by providing stable tools for assessment and planning the other – urban/agricultural - reuse possibilities (platform).</p> <p>Achieving significant Nutrient recovery from the WWTP concentrated streams upscaling the pilot technology demonstrated during the project and boosting market opportunities for the product obtained through new individuated CE business models (potential financing by Industries/stakeholder).</p> <p>Extending even at National/EU level the use of stable and transferable tools (platform) for the assessment of the different Sludge Management opportunities, to choose the most convenient for the environment by taking into account the economic sustainability. This will help to pursue more easily sludge valorisation, fostering the agricultural reuse.</p>
<p>List of stakeholders</p>	<p>Cross-cutting stakeholders:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Veneto Region, the main regional Authority (Regional level) • Metropolitan City of Venice, the Local Public administrative Authority (Provincial level) • City of Venice, Municipality (City level) • ARPAV (Regional Agency for the Environmental Prevention and Protection of Veneto) • Basin Council of Venice Lagoon, body of planning/control of the Integrated Water Service (IWS) (basin level, includes 36 municipalities) • VIVERACQUA, Consortium of Utilities for the IWS in the Veneto Region • Associations of Agriculture and Products: AMBIVENETO, Veneto Agricoltura • Industrial associations: UNINDUSTRIA • Universities: Ca' Foscari of Venice <p>Stakeholders SPECIFIC for each resource:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Water • <u>Agricultural sector</u>: Land Reclamation Board (ACQUE RISORGIVE, VENICE LAGOON Reclamation Board) • <u>Industrial sector</u>: SPM Porto Marghera Services (Consortium of Industries in PM); Ente Zona Industriale Porto Marghera (Operative structure of UNIndustria Venice); ENI S.p.A.; EDISON • Urban sector: Public/Private companies (like Hotel chains,...) investing in new

	<p>urbanization area near the Mestre train station</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Nutrients <p>Manufacturing industries interested in ammonium sulphate; Assofertilizzanti; Coldiretti</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Sludge • National observatory for Sludge; UTILITALIA LAGOON Reclamation Board) • <u>Industrial sector</u>: SPM Porto Marghera Services (Consortium of Industries in PM); Ente Zona Industriale Porto Marghera (Operative structure of UN Industria Venice); ENI S.p.A.; EDISON • Urban sector: Public/Private companies (e.g. hotel chains, ...) investing in new urbanization area near the Mestre train station
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3.2. Circular maps of stakeholders in each LL

Implementing circular economy initiatives requires an important level of coordination between different municipal departments in cities, as well as coordination between stakeholders. In this sense, some cities as Melbourne, Oulu or Toronto have created horizontal **working groups dedicated to the circular economy implementation**. For example, the working group created in the city of Toronto comprises 11 divisions (Solid Waste Management Services, Purchasing and Materials Management, Environment and Energy, Parks, Forestry and Recreation, City Planning, Economic Development and Culture, Corporate Real Estate Management, Toronto Public Health, Transportation Services, Toronto Water, and Engineering and Construction Services) (OECD 2020). The city of Rotterdam **co-created its four years programme on circular economy** involving all the departments concerned with circularity in the municipality. The Department of Economy in the city of Groningen, Netherlands, is working with the water, waste and international affairs Departments to develop a **circular economy strategy**. These are some examples of the importance of stakeholders in the circular economy strategy definition. In particular, **stakeholders coming from waste, water and food sectors are, usually, involved due to the role they are playing in managing waste**. In the framework of the B-WaterSmart project, a similar coordination will be needed, in order to implement CE strategies or pilot actions in the Living Labs. In the next point, we present the provisional stakeholder maps refer to the core/active actors to be involved in the CE business models in each LL which will be further completed within D1.1.

3.2.1. Stakeholders in Alicante Living Lab

Table 8: Alicante information about water-energy-waste stakeholders.

Category	Definition of subcategories
Living Lab Owner	Aguas de Alicante
Water	<p>Infrastructure owner EPSAR (public institution owner of the wastewater treatment facilities of Rincon de Leon)</p> <p>Operator and Regulator AMAEM (Aguas Municipalizadas de Alicante)</p> <p>Supervisory authority Drinking water - AMAEM (Aguas Municipalizadas de Alicante); Sewage - Cuenca Hidrografica (water basin administration)</p> <p>Relevant users (key sectors) Irrigation communities; Alicante municipality; agricultural parks; key industries</p>
Energy	Operator Regulator -
Waste	Regulator: Ministry for Ecological Transition
Relevant users (key sectors)	<p>CEMEX: cement industry (user of sewage sludge)</p> <p>Agricultural sector</p> <p>Sectoral organisations (agriculture, industry, etc)</p> <p>CE related organisations</p>

Figure 11: Circular map of preliminary stakeholders in Alicante.

Source: Cetaqua own elaboration.

3.2.2. Stakeholders in Bodø Living Lab

Table 9: Bodø information about water-energy-waste stakeholders.

Category	Definition of subcategories
Living Lab Owner	Bodø municipality
Key Govt agencies	The owner of the water plant is responsible for complying with the drinking water regulations. Most of the plants in Norway are owned by the municipalities. In smaller places, there are also private water treatment plants The Norwegian Food Safety Authority is responsible for approval, inspection and emergency preparedness.
Water	<p>Infrastructure owner The municipalities are owner of the infrastructure for drinking water and Sewage water. Some of the pipelines for drainage water are owned by private companies</p> <p>Operator and Regulator Bodø municipality (operator of water network)</p> <p>Supervisory authority Norwegian Food Safety authority (Drinking water); County governor (sewage)</p> <p>Relevant users (key sectors)</p>
Energy	Operator/ Regulator -
Waste	Operator/ Regulator -
Relevant users (key sectors)	IRIS: intermunicipal waste company - compost of sewage sludge The construction industry, technology companies/developers
CE related organizations or CE projects/initiatives ongoing	City Loops
Other followers' cities	Stakeholders: Bodø Energi Varme AS; AVINOR Followers: Stavenger Komune; Trondheim Kommune

Figure 12: Circular map of preliminary stakeholders in Bodø.

Source: Cetaqua own elaboration.

3.2.3. Stakeholders in East Frisia Living Lab

Table 10: East Frisia information about water-energy-waste stakeholders.

Category	Definition of subcategories
Living Lab Owner	Waterboard of Oldenburg and East Frisia (OOWV); OOWV (Lower Saxony) is one of the largest water services providers in Germany, with an area of 7,860 km ² , delivering drinking water from groundwater resources to private, industrial and agricultural customers (and treating wastewater in ~50% of the area).
Key Govt agencies	Environment agency
Water	<p>Infrastructure owner Drinking water supply OOWV; dairy business DMK</p> <p>Operator OOWV (Lower Saxony) is one of the largest water services providers in Germany, with an area of 7,860 km², delivering drinking water from groundwater resources to private, industrial and agricultural customers (and treating wastewater in ~50% of the area).</p>

	Regulator NLWKN, LAVES, Federal Environmental Agency Relevant users (key sectors) Dairy Industry, adaptation of technology in food industry
Energy	Operator/ Regulator – not considered in B-WaterSmart
Waste	Operator/ Regulator – not considered in B-WaterSmart
Relevant users (key sectors)	Key sectors: dairy industry, food industry, agriculture; Institutions responsible (Chamber of Agriculture Lower Saxony, Chamber of Commerce and Industry Lower Saxony) water boards/ water supply companies; technological providers
Other followers	Harz Water Works; Hessen Wasser, Interessensgemeinschaft norddeutsche Trinkwasserwerke

Figure 13: Circular map of preliminary stakeholders in East Frisia.

Source: Cetqua own elaboration

3.2.4. Stakeholders in Flanders Living Lab

Table 11: Flanders information about water-energy-waste stakeholders.

Category	Definition of subcategories
Living Lab owner	DeW (De Watergroep) PSKW (Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt)
Key Govt agencies	VMM (Regulatory body) City of Mechelen (project partner). Municipality of Diksmuide
Water	<p>Infrastructure owner</p> <p>Operator</p> <p>Drinking water is operated by public (municipality owned) companies, such as project partner De Watergroep; industrial process water is a private market where the public drinking water companies and others are active; household waste water is managed at the local level by municipalities (often public companies) and at a supra-municipal level by project partner Aquafin, who is also responsible for treatment; Aquafin designs, prefinances, builds and operates WWT plants; Aquafin is a public-private owned company; industrial waste water treatment and process water production is a private market, where many private companies are active, but also (subsidiaries of) the public companies such as De Watergroep and Aquafin. Other relevant water utilities in the region are Pidpa (city of Mechelen), IWVA.</p> <p>Regulator</p> <p>VMM is the Environment Agency of the region, and is responsible for regulation and permitting of environmental issues including (waste) water; they are also responsible for reporting of the state of the environment towards the EU (WFD etc.)</p> <p>Supervisory authority</p> <p>Regional environment agency, De Vlaamse waterweg (for navigable rivers), the province or a local water body ('polders' and 'wateringen') is responsible; for drinking water public companies (owned by municipalities) are responsible for water provision and distribution in their geographical region; process water management and distribution is a private market; waste water treatment management is done by municipal companies at a local level and by Aquafin at a regional level - Aquafin is responsible for treatment.</p> <p>Relevant users (key sectors)</p> <p>Key sectors: wastewater treatment, horticulture; water management is based on stream size, not on sectors; VMM is the overarching responsible public body.</p>
Energy	<p>Operator energy production is also a private market</p> <p>Regulator-</p>
Waste	<p>Operator</p> <p>Waste services (not-water) is a private market;</p> <p>Regulator:</p>

	<p>VMM is the Environment Agency of the region, and is responsible for regulation and permitting of environmental issues including (waste) water; they are also responsible for reporting of the state of the environment towards the EU (WFD etc)</p>
<p>Relevant users (key sectors)</p>	<p>Stakeholders: case De Watergroep: mainly project partner de Watergroep and local water managing authorities (VMM, Zuidijzerpolder); case Mechelen: municipality, farmers and farmer unions, VMM (water manager).</p> <p>Agricultural sector (Boerenbond, ABS); Drinking water sector (Aquaflanders); Polder management organisations.</p>

Figure 14: Circular map of preliminary stakeholders in Flanders.

Source: Cetaqua own elaboration.

3.2.5. Stakeholders in Lisbon Living Lab

Table 12: Lisbon information about water-energy-waste stakeholders.

Category	Definition of subcategories
Living Lab Owner	Lisbon municipality
Key Govern agencies	APA (Portuguese Environment Agency), ERSAR (Regulator for Water and Waste Services)
Water	<p>Infrastructure owner EPAL (water supply utility); AdTA; Lisbon municipality</p> <p>Operator EPAL (water supply utility); AdTA (sanitation utility)</p> <p>Regulator ERSAR (water and waste services regulator)</p> <p>Supervisory authority APA (Portuguese Environment Agency)</p> <p>Relevant users (key sectors) Key sectors: construction, infrastructure, landscaping, agriculture, industry (Large consumers include hospitals, universities and large retailers); 49,5% consumption is domestic; 25,6% trade and industry; http://www.observatorios-lisboa.pt/en/agua.html</p>
Energy	<p>Operator Energy production is also a private market; Important stakeholders: EDP (this was the public company that was privatised; so far, it is still the main distributor and network operator - this could change with coming tenders; it is also the largest commercialiser; other commercialises include GALP, ENDESA, IBERDROLA, etc.</p> <p>Regulator: ERSE (Regulator Authority for Energy Services)</p> <p>Main users: Main users are services (67%), followed by domestic consumption (23%) http://www.observatorios-lisboa.pt/en/energia.html</p>
Waste	<p>Operator: ValorSul (private company, public shareholders)</p> <p>Regulator: ERSAR (Regulator for Water and Waste Services)</p>
Relevant users (key sectors)	There are several organisations licenced to do packaging, medical supplies and other materials' recycling; we can reach out if there is a role for them in the project

	<p>APRH (association of water professionals & utilities); APDA (association of water utilities)</p> <p>APESB (association of water professionals & utilities); AEPESA (technology providers association)</p> <p>PPA (Portuguese Water Partnership); ANQIP (National Association for Quality in Built Environments; developed an equipment certification for water efficiency)</p>
CE related organisms	Centro circular economy (CCDRC)
Other follower cities	Cascais Ambiente (Municipality of Cascais); Municipality of Torres Vedras; Metropolitan Area of Lisbon and its 18 municipalities

Figure 15: Circular map of preliminary stakeholders in Lisbon.

Source: Cetaqua own elaboration.

3.2.6. Stakeholders in Venice Living Lab

Table 13: Venice information about water-energy-waste stakeholders.

Category	Definition of subcategories
Living Lab Owner	VERITAS S.p.A.
Key Govt agencies	<p>The VENETO REGION is the main administrative division of the Region, responsible for the National Law contextualization in the territory (with some margin of modifications only if more restrictive) and for some authoritative procedures (particular discharges in the environment) or treatment/plant significant upgrade and new Plant designing.</p> <p>The METROPOLITAN CITY of VENICE (Provincial level) is the Local Public administrative Authority for the integrated environmental management and pollution control; manages some authoritative procedures for treatment plants and discharges.</p>
Water	<p>Infrastructure owner and Operator</p> <p>VERITAS is the Public multi-utility responsible for wastewater, waste and drinking water management for a territory of 51 municipalities and 1 Million inhabitants; (a similar role is played by ETRA).</p> <p>VIVERACQUA, a Consortium of Utilities for the integrated water service in the Veneto Region, has the goal to scale-up the economy of some common processes (i.e. energy and other products acquiring)</p> <p>Regulator</p> <p>Regional Authority and local scale: VENETO REGION and Metropolitan City of Venice</p> <p>VERITAS is the main responsible for wastewater and drinking water management (a similar role is played by ETRA).</p> <p>ARERA: Italian Regulatory Authority for Electricity, Gas and Water (key variables for the management assessment; tariff regulations).</p> <p>Supervisory authority</p> <p>Technical organisms of control ARPAV (Regional Agency for the Environmental Prevention and Protection of Veneto), the main agency that monitors natural resources and water discharge compliance.</p>
Energy	<p>Operator</p> <p>ENI and ENEL are the main companies operating in the energy sector.</p> <p>Regulator</p> <p>ARERA: Italian Regulatory Authority for Electricity, Gas and Water (key variables for the management assessment; tariff regulations).</p>

<p>Waste</p>	<p>Operator</p> <p>VERITAS is the main responsible for waste management (a similar role is played by ETRA).</p> <p>Regulator</p> <p>National level: Parliament (National level) and the Ministry of Environment (MATTM), ISPRA (Superior Institute for Environmental Protection and Research).</p> <p>Regional level: ARPAV (Regional Agency for the Environmental Prevention and Protection of Veneto).</p>
<p>Relevant users (key sectors)</p>	<p>Water:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agricultural sector: Land Reclamation Board (ACQUE RISORGIVE; V LAGOON Rec Board). • Industrial sector: SPM Porto Marghera Services – Consortium of Industries in PM; Ente Zona Industriale Porto Marghera - operative structure of UNIndustria Venice; ENI S.p.A.; EDISON. • Urban sector: Public/Private companies (like Hotel chains,...) investing in new urbanization area near the Mestre train station. <p>Nutrients:</p> <p>Manufacturing industries interested in ammonium sulphate; Assofertilizzanti; Coldiretti</p> <p>Sludge:</p> <p>National observatory for sludge; UTILITALIA; ARPAV; VIVERACQUA</p> <p>Cross-cutting stakeholders:</p> <p>Veneto Region: Main regional Authority (Regional level)</p> <p>Metropolitan City of Venice Local Public administrative Authority (Provincial level)</p> <p>City Of Venice Municipality (City level)</p> <p>ARPAV (Regional Agency for the Environmental Prevention and Protection of Veneto)</p> <p>Basin Council of Venice Lagoon: body of planning/control of Integrated Water Service (IWS) (basin level – 36 municipalities)...</p> <p>Utilities: VIVERACQUA - Consortium of Utilities for the IWS in the Veneto Region.</p> <p>Associations of Agriculture and Products: AMBIVENETO, Veneto Agricoltura...</p> <p>Industrial Associations: UNINDUSTRIA..</p> <p>Universities: Ca' Foscari, ...</p>

Figure 16: Circular map of preliminary stakeholders in Venice.

Source: Cetaqua own elaboration.

4. Data specifications and type of information required from the Living Labs

Cities where these LLs labs are located have a density and concentration of businesses and citizens that generate material and resource flows with potential for circularity. They have a scale that enables **quick decisions**, building on the autonomous power to regulate and incentivise, and they are large enough to enable the **establishment of new circular city functions and services**, and **circular business models**.

Administrations and their main territorial actors can define and communicate their **circular vision**, define a **circular strategy** and embed **circular principles** in city functions and services, and thus create a good framework for the **circular transition**. **Living Labs** can also lead offering and/or **procuring circular solutions and services**, build **circular awareness** and promote a culture of **collaboration among all stakeholders**. A circular city must also fully realise and exploit its potential to be a **cradle for circular development** and use its governance tools and levers as **catalysts for circular change** (EIB, 2018).

The **challenge of becoming circular cities** needs to be measured through **data information**. **Data must be collected from their key territorial actors** to identify **circular opportunities** (data that will be collected during T4.2. in the framework of WP4 of the B-WaterSmart project). The OECD (2020) insists on the need of circular economy measurement frameworks for a) **measuring progress and impacts of circular-economy-related initiatives and raising awareness of the circular economy and related opportunities**; b) **making the case for the circular economy applying CE principles from an environmental, economic and social point of view**; c) **triggering actions** design circular economy strategies and support policy-makers in setting policy priorities on the basis of urban metabolism analyses; d) **monitoring performance and evaluating results**. During Task 4.2., Cetaqua will define the circular indicators which will measure the circularity of the opportunities identified in each Living Lab (Deliverable 4.2.).

Figure 17 shows the different steps to be followed in collecting the data, from information needs to final results. The upper part of the figure is related to the different steps for indicators and the bottom is related to the framework for action based on the compiled data. The middle part is the sequence to follow in order to achieve the results envisaged.

Figure 17: Procedure (steps) and framework of circularity data in the context of B-WaterSmart project.

Source: Cetaqua own elaboration

- 1. Goal and scope** - After the context definition (Chapter 1 and 2) and the characterization of each LL, followed by the definition of preliminary stakeholders and circular maps (Chapter 3), a relevant step is to define the specific goal(s) for each LL, as well as the scope that the project will seek to achieve in the context of circularity. Here, the proposal is to include the context of application, complementary methods and actions aimed at integrating stakeholders' views, impact on externalities, dependencies and influences.
- 2. Inventory and data acquisition** - First, template questionnaires need to be elaborated for each Living Lab according to the request and definition detailed in the step 1 for each LL. These acquiring data will be collected during Task 4.2 for each stakeholder involved in each System study for each Living Lab according to the water-energy-waste-materials nexus and their current business models.
- 3. Circularity identification** - From technical point of view, with information related to water-energy-waste-materials nexus among the system values and their stakeholders involved, new opportunities more circular to connect/adapt/propose their gaps will be identified for each Living Lab (task 4.2) with new/readapt business models (Task 4.3.).
- 4. Circularity measurement** - To measure the circularity of opportunities identified in 6 Living Labs, several circular indicators will be defined through Deliverable 4.2 (Task 4.2, Task 4.3) to measure the circularities of circular opportunities identified. These circular indicators will take into account the three axes' indicators -environmental, economic, social viability according different typologies (water, energy, waste, material).
- 5. Circularity assessment** - To quantify the circular assessment applying the indicators to the defined circularities to assure/evaluate their impacts and trade-offs, interpreting results to

target audience and users of result intended application domain of the result provided from applying the framework. An action plan for each circularity in each Living Lab will be elaborated and their financial instruments identified (Task 4.4).

The following subsections, 4.1 and 4.2, contain the technical and social data, as well as economic data, to be collected from the Living Labs, in order to define the circular economy opportunities during Task 4.2., as well as develop circular business models in Task 4.3.

4.1. Technical data required for Living Labs

Section 4.1 provides an overview of different data categories that will be required in each Living Lab in order to assess circular economy opportunities. Specific forms, surveys or questionnaires will be elaborated and adapted to each relevant stakeholder on all Living Labs once the mapping of stakeholders and their prioritisation are completed in D1.1. (CoPs architecture and stakeholder mapping for each LL, to be published in May 2021). Overall, technical data that will be required can be classified under the following categories (Table 14):

Table 14: Categories of data.

Water-related data	Water balances (input-output) including water consumption from each identified source; required water quality for each use and generated wastewater flows including discharge point or wastewater quality . Information about own water and wastewater treatments when it applies. Data focusing on wastewater reclamation, such as existence of reclamation processes; internal water reclamation for industrial stakeholders or existence and characterisation of the reclaimed water distribution network in the area if it exists. Percentage of urban wastewater reclaimed over total treated or percentage of water consumed from alternative sources (wastewater reclamation, seawater desalination) over water from conventional sources.
Energy consumption and generation	Overall energy consumption , including electricity and other forms of energy (e.g. heat, steam); fraction of self-produced energy; energy-related data to energy consumption levels (e.g. biofuel consumption; energy efficiency in buildings and homes; and electrical energy consumption), energy recovery valorisation (waste heat valorisation or biogas production and cogeneration).
Type of waste and emissions	Type of waste generated, fraction that is valorised (% recycling rate), fraction that is landfilled or goes to other destinations; emissions to soil and air. Concerning waste , indicators are mostly related to the environment category. Indicators concern both waste generation and management. Waste indicators also distinguish across categories of waste, such as biowaste, plastics or electronic waste. Waste destination differentiates across landfill, incinerated waste, recycled waste composting or any other valorisation route. Waste recycling : Recycling rates for different types of wastes/materials; recycled material quality compared with virgin material quality; turnover of key recyclables; and environmental effects and cost/revenues of municipal waste management in Europe. Data related to the air category refers to emissions of CO ₂ (carbon dioxide) and GHGs (Greenhouse gases) and are all included in the environmental category. However, most cities and regions have difficulties in the collection of reliable data for emissions measurement (indicative sampling could give an estimate).

Materials inputs and products outflows data	For each intended outflow, mass of outflow, actual average technical lifetime of material/product (Baseline), fraction of content that is eventually recycled, recycling efficiency, fraction of content that is renewable, fraction of reuse content, fraction of recycled content.
Industrial sectors	Specific sectors such as food and beverage sector have a high relevance when measuring circularity, especially in terms of waste: the amount of food waste generated, the number of food recovery-redistribution actions and food waste avoided through a circular consumption. Other interesting industries data (e.g. working group meetings with major industry players for better regulatory alignment as a boost to the circular economy); agriculture (seed banks and agro-ecological initiatives); mobility (car sharing and use of private vehicles in cities); forestry (direct jobs associated with the forest/wood sector); and tourism (number of tourism enterprises and productivity of the sustainable tourism sector)
Data for built environment	Covering the whole life cycle of buildings , from the design (e.g. construction works with circular design and projects incorporating smart design) to end of life (e.g. recovery rate of construction and demolition waste, the recovery rate of construction waste as material). This data also addresses the existence of circular-economy-related certifications for buildings (e.g. certification based on life cycle or eco-design , percentage of construction projects applying to certification programmes and the inclusion of eco-designed products).

Circular economy data will be split up in several categories according to the prevision of future circular economy indicators: **environment, governance, economic and business, infrastructure and technology and social.**

Technical data regarding the **environmental flux** will collect data related emissions, output material process and production and consumption efficiency, savings, use, material flows (exports and imports), the self-sufficiency of materials and the recovery of materials; the **governance aspect** focuses on data related to capacity building and regulation, among others as awareness-raising, capacity building, collaboration, education, financing, innovation, pilots and experiments, monitoring and evaluation, public procurement, regulation and stakeholder engagement; **infrastructure and technology** will cover all the data to measure the existence of tools, technologies and spaces that boost the circular economy, equipment, facilities, products and services; jobs related to data associated with employment and human resources.

Other general data with 360° vision from LLs and stakeholders will be collected to elaborate different indicators according to the OECD proposals:

- **Output material process** includes data for indicators measuring the various phases of waste and material that can be reused and transformed into resources.
- **Production and consumption** cover data materials and resources that have been used in the economy, mostly in the generation of waste measured in several sectors (e.g. construction, industry, municipal, energy, virgin materials and water consumption).

- **Use** describes data for those indicators on the utilisation and reuse of resources (e.g. amount of resources used and reintegrated into the system; direct resource use; and direct land use), as well as several use rates (e.g. circular material use rate and reuse of packaging waste) **and savings-efficiency** refers to data indicators mentioning the consumption avoidance and savings of different resources such as energy, food and raw materials.
- **Products and services** (new circular products and share of circular products in the total number).
- **Awareness-raising** data for indicators mainly refer to the number of awareness-raising campaigns and events organised for different areas (e.g. food waste reduction, plastic use reduction and water reuse). However, data collected to elaborate related indicators account also for other ways of raising awareness and disseminating circular economy principles in the format of workshops, events, publications, guidelines and platforms. Data to monitor the role of the **public administration** as a driver for the circular economy: e.g. the number of municipal staff trained on the circular economy; the economic savings from the reuse of furniture and equipment of the local administration; and the number of municipal staff actively working on the development of a circular vision.
- **Innovation, pilots and experiments**, these indicators primarily include indicators related to the implementation of research and development (R&D) pilots and projects: e.g. the creation of an innovation platform for the circular economy, the number of experimental and pilot projects, the number of circular-economy-related R&D projects and the number of actors involved in experimental projects in the context of B-WaterSmart.
- **Strategy and initiatives** data indicators generally monitor the number of initiatives adopted (e.g. agro-ecological initiatives, projects incorporating smart design, green and circular initiatives and number of water reuse projects). Furthermore, they analyse the different circular initiatives adopted by local authorities, as well as the steps for their adoption, the level of implementation and the number of documents created.
- **Public procurement:** this category includes indicators linked to the inclusion of circular and green criteria in the purchasing of goods, services and works by governments. Several indicators account for the volume of public procurement that includes circular and/or ecological criteria (measured as a percentage of total procurement, number of tenders or total amount in euros). Other indicators address the number of identified legal barriers for the implementation of green public procurement (GPP), or the number of companies informed about circular-economy-related public procurement opportunities.
- **Capacity-building** indicators address the number of training courses on the circular economy, and the different activities to build knowledge of the circular economy. Indicators distinguish the training courses aimed at municipal staff (e.g. city staff trained in circular economy and circular procurement principles; and the number of training modules created for municipal staff). Other examples of this sub-category are training courses and their level of implementation in the circular economy, conferences and seminars for improving skills, support programmes and guides.
- **Regulation:** Data to elaborate indicators within this category focus on the creation and update of the existing regulation to boost the circular economy and the identification and removal of identified regulatory barriers. Indicators not only focus on the results and achievements but

also on the entire process (e.g. number of working group meetings to work on better legislation and the number of circular policy advisers developing circular regulations). **Stakeholder engagement** data for indicators mainly focus on actions to engage with key actors involved in all phases of the circular economy initiative (design, implementation and monitoring). For instance, the number of the circular economy vision-forming meetings, the number of actors mobilised, the number of collaborative projects implemented by circular economy networks and the number of meetings for circular projects. The inventory also collects data/indicators on **collaboration** activities, involving all actions related to co-operation among different actors' synergies, projects and workshops to boost a circular economy. Indicators measure the way collaboration frameworks are built, by monitoring the number of meetings of working groups to boost the circular economy. In the context of B-WaterSmart this information will be collected of Communities of Practice creation (WP1). Other indicators aim to measure the implementation of the collaboration frameworks such as the number of collaborative projects implemented, or the implementation of identified synergies.

4.2. Socio-Economic data required

The adaptation of current BMs or the development of new ones for circular economy opportunities detected in each LL requires several variables to be gathered from them. In order to collect data and information about the existing BMs, the model selected is the **Triple-Layered Business Model Canvas** (Joyce and Paquin, 2010), a framework for conceptualizing CBMs that redesigns Business Model Canvas (BMC) to integrate economic, social and environmental exchanges into a holistic view of BMs value creation.

The model consists of three separate BMC, one for each pillar of sustainability, that are interconnected to support more broadly the circular value creation within a company. As shown in Figure 18, it extends the original economic-oriented BMC by adding two layers: an environmental layer, based on a lifecycle perspective, and a social layer, based on a stakeholder perspective (Joyce and Paquin, 2016).

Figure 18: Triple Layered business model canvas (TLBMC)

Source: Joyce and Paquin, 2016

Economic layer

Original economic BMC contains nine interlinked building blocks, which cover the four main areas of a business: customers, offer, infrastructure, and financial viability (Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2010). Although it is focused in organizations, we will use this approach for different circular opportunities detected in each living lab, and depending on the kind of opportunity detected, an adaptation will be required.

The following BMC template (Table 15) summarizes the relevant questions that might be answered in order to redesign BMs in each LL.

Table 15: BMC template.

Source: Adapted from Osterwalder and Pigneur, 2010 and EMF, 2016

Customer segments	<p>For whom are we creating value? Who are our most important customers? Who else might benefit from or will be affected by your materials/product/service? <i>Examples: Niche or mass market; upper/middle/lower segment; diversified and multi-sided platforms/markets.</i></p>
Value proposition	<p>What value we deliver to customer? Quantitative (e.g., price, speed of service, efficiency) or qualitative (e.g., circular design, customer experience, incentives and benefits for customers for bringing back used products)? Which one of our customers' problems are we trying to solve? What are the needs we are aiming to meet? Is it a product or is a service required to fulfil these needs? Is there anything associated with our product/service that has potential value to others?</p>
Channels	<p>Through which channels we deliver, communicate and sell value propositions? Through which channels do our customer segments want to be reached? how are we reaching them now? How are our channels integrated between them and with customer routines? Are well-integrated and cost-efficient? How might we redesign our relationship with our supply chain? How might we build feedback loops directly into our product/service that allow you to identify new opportunities? What role could we play in the reverse logistics chain?</p>
Customer relationships	<p>What type of relationship does each of our customer segments expect us to establish and maintain with them? Which ones have we established? How costly are they? How are they integrated with the rest of our business model? How might you connect customers with other parts of the journey of your product/service or materials?</p>
Revenue streams	<p>What amount are our customers really willing to pay? What do they currently pay? What is our pricing mechanism? How are they currently paying? How would they prefer to pay? How much does each Revenue Stream contribute to overall revenues? How might we diversify opportunities to increase resilience, growth and innovation? How might our business model help create other types of value? Human, social or natural capital? How might new services increase revenue from existing products, assets or your delivery systems? How might value generated from products/components/materials or energy captured from waste disposal?</p>
Key resources	<p>What key resources do our value proposition, channels, customer relationships and revenue streams require? Where will your resources come from (renewable or finite source) and what will happen to them after use? What capabilities do you need to enable circular flows and feedback mechanisms and run your organisation successfully in the short and long term?</p>

Key activities	<p>What Key Activities do our VP, C, CR and RS require?</p> <p>What activities might best help to achieve our value proposition?</p> <p>What might be the positive externalities of our KA? And how might we monitor and design out any negative externalities?</p> <p>How might we create new forms of human, natural or financial capital?</p>
Key partnerships	<p>Who are our key partners (stakeholders, key alliances, etc.)? Who are our key suppliers?</p> <p>Which key resources are we acquiring from partners?</p> <p>Which key activities partners perform?</p> <p>How might we strengthen our partnerships with organisations across the value chain to benefit from circularity (flows of materials, information and capital) in the system?</p> <p>What new or unexpected partnerships can we form to grow circularity within our organisation and the system?</p>
Cost structure	<p>What are the most important costs inherent in our business model (manufacturing costs, R&D costs, financial costs, economies of scale, etc.)?</p> <p>Which key resources and key activities are most expensive?</p> <p>Which costs could be shared or lowered through other users and partners?</p> <p>Could we shift from an ownership model of underutilised assets to payment for access and usage?</p> <p>How might we reduce cost volatility and dependence on the use of finite resources?</p>

In this context, it is also necessary to collect the following circular economy data, which will allow to develop **circular economic and business** indicators according to the OECD proposals:

Table 16: Circular economic and business indicators

Business Data	Performance of companies and the introduction of business models such as new revenue models related to the circular economy and the number of companies implementing product-as-a-service business models and other circular business models.
Financing and Investment's data	Data refer to all the economic support provided by governments to conduct a circular initiative (e.g., public expenditure in R&D related to the circular economy, the budget amount assigned to calls for projects and budget of pilot public contracts in the circular economy) and private investment in R&D, goods and projects related to the circular economy
Saving measures	Includes all financial resources saved in certain circular actions (e.g., money saved, in comparison with purchasing new) through the reuse of building materials; reduced costs through the implementation of green procurement; and the economic savings due to the reuse of furniture of the local administration and waste reduction.
Productivity	Measures the amount of economic output generated per unit of material.
Added value	Is related to the value generation created by the circular economy and circular

	activities (e.g., the economic value of the resources used, and gross value added generated).
Economic efficiency	Economic efficiency measure materials and energy intensity in monetary terms.
Gains and revenues	Gains and revenues obtained through performing actions closely related to the circular economy (e.g., turnover on circular products and economic gains of the reduction of the digital impact in the public administration).
Economic structure	Include data for indicators such as the weight of the green economy in GDP and GDP per total GHG emissions.
Employment and Human Resources data	This data distinguishes between employment within circular economy generic activities and job creation in specific circular economy sectors such as the sharing economy, the reuse and repair sector and the forestry sector. For example, the number of green jobs created and secured, the net circular job growth, and the number of jobseekers having been employed as a result of circular economy training.

Environmental layer

The fundamental aim of the environmental layer is to assess how the organization generates more environmental benefits than environmental impacts, identifying the most critical environmental issues and the most important practices of circularity and sustainability that is undertaking (García Muiña et al., 2020). For this purpose, is based on a view of the entire life cycle from a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) perspective. The components of this layer are shown in the following table (Joyce and Paquin, 2016) (Table 17):

Table 17: Environmental Layer template.

Functional value	Describes the focal outputs of a product/service. This value corresponds to the functional unit used in the LCA analysis conducted on the company.
Materials	Materials is the environmental extension of the key resources block of BMC. The heading “materials” represents the bio-physical stocks used to render the functional value.
Production	Production incorporates the key activities component from the original BMC and focuses on the core activities that the organization undertakes to create value. For example, for a manufacturer may involve transforming raw or unfinished materials into higher value outputs for a service provider can involve running an IT infrastructure, transporting people or other logistics, using office spaces and hosting service points.
Supplies and	This block refers to all the other materials and production activities that are

out-sourcing	necessary for the functional value but not defined as central to the organization.
Distribution	As in the BMC, refers to the transportation of the outputs. In the environmental layer, it is the combination of the transportation modes, the distances travelled and the weights of what is shipped as well as issues of packaging and delivery logistics.
Use phase	The use phase focuses on customers participation in the functional value or core product/service. This includes the necessary resources that the client must employ for the use and maintenance of the product and should include some consideration of the client's material resource and energy requirements through use.
End-of-life	The last phase is the end-of-life phase. In this context, it should be considered how the end of life is managed by the customer. This often require issues of material reuse such as remanufacturing, repurposing, recycling, etc.
Environmental impacts	This component examines the ecological costs of the organization's actions, as with exploring an organization's financial costs, this provides an opportunity to identify where are its biggest environmental impacts. There are multiple indicators that can be used to evaluate environmental impacts (e.g., CO _{2e} emissions, ecosystems quality, resource and energy consumption, water use, human health, etc.).
Environmental benefits	The environmental benefits extend the concept of value creation, considering the ecological value the organization creates through environmental impact reductions and regenerative positive ecological value. For example, applying a circular model has positive environmental impacts like efficient consumption of resources by treating and reusing wastewater.

Social Layer

The social layer extends the traditional BMC through a stakeholder approach to both capture the mutual influences between stakeholders and the organization. The scope of this model is to understand the major social impacts derived from relations with key stakeholders through these components (Joyce and Paquin, 2016) (Table 18):

Table 18: Social Layer template.

Local community	Local community must be the first to be analysed, while economic relationships are built with business partners, there are social relationships established between the company and the stakeholders present on the company's territory, including suppliers. These two stakeholders come together as communities when aligning the three layers of the TLBMC.
Social value	Social value is the part of the corporate mission that focuses on how to create benefits for stakeholders and society.

Employees	Employees are considered as a core organizational stakeholder. This component includes characteristics and management of the workforce (e.g., amounts and types of employees, salient demographics such as variations pay, gender, ethnicity, employee-oriented programs, etc.)
Governance	Governance explains the organizational structure and decision-making policies of an organization. It is possible to consider different structure frameworks such as organizational hierarchy, functional vs. unit specialization; privately-owned companies vs. publicly traded companies, etc.
Social culture	This component represents the potential impact of an organization on society as a whole. The focus is on the potential actions of the company that can positively or negatively influence society.
Scale of outreach	The scale of outreach provides information on the type of the relationship between the company and its stakeholders. This relationship could be based on the short-term interest of both parties or on a long-term perspective and, also, in terms of geographical area, could be focused on the local territory or act from a global perspective.
End-user	The end-user is the person who consumes the value proposition. This space is concerned with how the value proposition addresses the needs of the end-user, contributing to his/her quality of life. Users with similar needs have typically been segmented based on relevant demographics e e.g., age, income, ethnicity, education level, etc. Importantly, the end-user is not always the customer as defined in the economic layer of the business model canvas. For instance, textbook publishers historically consider course instructors as customers though students are the end-users.
Social impacts	Social impacts are the social costs of an organization that complement and extend the financial costs of the economic layer and the bio-physical impacts of the environmental layer. The choice of social impact measures depends on the nature of the organization, some of the most common indicators are: working hours, cultural heritage, health and safety, community engagement, fair competition, etc. (Benoît-Norris et al. 2011).
Social benefits	Social benefits, with social impacts, are the core of the social BMCs. This component considers the social benefits derived from organization's actions such as community engagement, personal development through training programs, etc.

5. Conclusions

- Although urban population is increasing in the world, the increase in Europe will be less of 1%, more than 60% of European population is living in urban areas.
- **Urban spaces** are covering 7% of land area and are using 75% of annual **resource use**, 75% of **carbon emissions**, 80% of **energy consumption** and are generating 70% of global **waste consumption** (UN DESA, 2014, UNEP 2013). For this reason, cities and regions should act as agents of change towards sustainable development.
- **Circular economy is emerging as a different approach for driving sustainable development** and is gaining momentum as a new way of acting.
- European Commission is strongly committed with circular economy along the lines of the EU **Circular Economy Action Plan** (2020), which attributes an important role to cities and local territories in implementing the transition towards a CE model as one of the main pillars of the **European Green Deal (2019)**, the new agenda for sustainable growth in Europe.
- Nevertheless, circular **database** and indicator frameworks are still **not developed for some national strategies or are still in development**.
- New development model for cities based on circular economy are driving the transition to circular cities, considering built environment, energy systems, urban mobility, urban bioeconomy and production systems.
- The circular economy transition in cities have different **environmental, institutional and socioeconomic drivers**. But, some **barriers** (technological, market and financial, institutional and regulatory) and gaps (funding, regulatory, policy, awareness, capacity) are still in place.
- Action for circular economy transition in cities include different phases but monitoring and measuring progress is an important one.
- **Business models** support the transition to the circular economy and describes how and organization create, deliver and capture value.
- There is no clear consensus in the literature on what is and is not a CBM but based on literature, CBMs can be defined **as business models that are cycling, extending, intensifying, and/or dematerialising material and energy loops** to reduce the resource inputs into and the waste and emission leakage out of an organisational system.
- **Related to water**, the incorporation of the principles of circular economy and smart solutions will allow to incorporate a smart sustainable management in water systems.
- However, it is important to include **other dimensions of water**, in other words, water transports nutrients, chemicals and minerals and is a source of energy in order to broaden the strategy due to the links with **energy, agriculture, industry, food production, waste and environment in the cities**. For this reason, it is necessary to think on **multi-sectoral water CE approaches** based on economic and environmental sectors and using and managing different resources.
- Digital technologies and smart solutions are not enough implemented for water circular economy that should be supported by the creation, extraction, processing and sharing data.
- From the water perspective, circular models in cities should focus on the sectors with strong linkages with water as energy, waste and food.
- Proposed strategy relies on **mapping key actors (public and private), collecting data to perform flow analysis, detect and map circular opportunities, setting a roadmap taking into account implementation issues as possible business models, ways of governance**

and finding, prioritisation and implementation circular opportunities under an action plan and monitoring and quantifying impacts of different measures using circular indicators defined.

- Nevertheless, one of the key challenges is **data gathering, management and analysis**
- Communities of Practices or **Living Labs** are **articulators between different actors to take off the circularity in regions or cities.**
- **In our case, circular economy initiatives and characterizations** for 6 B-WaterSmart regions: **Alicante, Bodø, East Frisia, Flanders, Lisbon, Venice are developed concerning preliminary mapping of stakeholders and circular initiatives.**
- Previous work was made under these categories: Environmental conditions/indicators, Socio-economic aspects/issues, Systemic Innovation on Water Smartness, Policy Regulation and Governance System. Each category is divided in some subcategories:
- Once characterization under these previous categories is done, collection of data is the next step under next needs:
 - a. **Goal and scope** - the proposal is to include the context of application, complementary methods and actions aimed at integrating stakeholders' views, impact on externalities, dependencies and influences.
 - b. **Inventory and data acquisition** -, template questionnaires need to be elaborated for each Living Lab according to the request and definition detailed in the previous step for each LL. according to the water-energy-waste-materials nexus and their current business models.
 - c. **Circularity identification** - From technical point of view, with information related to water-energy-waste-materials nexus among the system values and their stakeholders involved, new opportunities more circular to connect/adapt/propose their gaps will be identified for each Living Lab (task 4.2) with new/readapt business models (Task 4.3.).
 - d. **Circularity measurement** - To measure the circularity of opportunities identified in 6 Living Labs, several circular indicators will be defined through Deliverable 4.2 (Task 4.2, Task 4.3) to measure the circularities of circular opportunities identified. These circular indicators will take into account the three axes' indicators -environmental, economic, social viability according different typologies (water, energy, waste, material).
 - e. **Circularity assessment** - To quantify the circular assessment applying the indicators to the defined circularities to assure/evaluate their impacts and trade-offs, interpreting results to target audience and users of result intended application domain of the result provided from applying the framework. An action plan for each circularity in each Living Lab will be elaborated and their financial instruments identified (Task 4.4).
- Required data includes technical and socio-economic data. **Technical data** will include water-related data, energy consumption and generation data, type of waste and emission data, material inputs and products outflows data, industrial sectors data and built environmental data. **Socio-economic data** includes a triple-layered business model Canvas with economic, environmental and social layer.

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7. Supplementary information

7.1. Circular Economy initiatives in Living Labs regions

7.1.1. Alicante, Spain

National circularity strategy processes often involve consultation with subnational and local entities. This is the case of Spain, where in 2018, the **Spanish Circular Economy Strategy** incorporated almost 2 thousand observations from autonomous regions, the Spanish Federation of Municipalities and Provinces and citizens. The **Spanish Circular Economy Strategy 2030** was jointly promoted in 2018 by the Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries, Food and the Environment and the Ministry of Economy, Industry and Competitiveness. An inter-ministerial commission formed by nine ministries and the Economic Office of the President at that time contributed to it, together with the autonomous communities and the Spanish Federation of Municipalities and Provinces, proposed the Spanish Strategy on the Circular Economy which was approved in June 2020 by the Council of Ministers. The strategy is one of the key elements of **the Circular Economy Framework**, one of the government's projects that aims to be a lever for economic recovery after the COVID-19 health crisis. The adoption of the Spanish Circular Economy Strategy was foreseen in the **Declaration of Climate and Environmental Emergency** approved in January 2020, making it one of the priority lines of action, and is consistent with the draft bill on **Climate Change and Energy Transition**, which sets the goal of achieving **climate neutrality by 2050**. In addition, on June 2020, the Council of Ministers approved the draft bill on **Waste and Contaminated Soils**, which will also address the challenge of single-use plastics, and a royal decree to improve the traceability and control of waste routes.

The **Spanish Circular Economy Strategy** for 2030 sets out the basis for a new model of production and consumption in which the **value of products, materials and resources** is maintained in the economy for as long as possible, in which the generation of waste is minimised and those that cannot be avoided are used to the greatest possible extent.

In this context, the strategy establishes strategic orientations and sets a series of objectives to be achieved by 2030 [S Government, 2020]:

- Reduce **the consumption** of materials by 30% compared to 2010.
- Reduce **waste generation** by 15% compared to 2010.
- Reduce **waste food** generation.
- Increase the **reutilization**.
- Reduce **the greenhouse gas** emissions.
- Improve the **efficiency** of the water usage.

Moreover, the strategy identifies **six priority sectors of activity** in which to incorporate this challenge for a circular Spain: **construction, agri-food, fisheries and forestry, industry, consumer goods, tourism and textiles and clothing**.

Projects in Spain

ECO-circular is an innovative platform created for the diffusion of good practices in the application of the circular economy criteria. In this platform, there are published real experiences of different companies about the circular economy in Spain and Latin America [Ecocircular 2021].

ECOALF is a fashion brand that creates clothes from recycled materials with a sustainable production based on quality and a temporal design as a sign of durability and responsibility and no overproduction. In addition, they have created a foundation to promote the selective management of waste to recycle it, recover it and avoid its harmful impact on the environment. This foundation created in 2015, in Spain, the **Upcycling the oceans**, which aims to clean the oceans of marine waste with the help of the fishing industry and to give plastic waste a new life through recycling and the circular economy. They are currently working in Spain, Greece, Italy, and Thailand [Ecoalf 2021].

Ecoembes, a recycling company in Spain, has launched the **The Circular Lab**, which is an innovation centre specialized in circular economy and focuses its activity in the research and development of best practices in the field of packaging and its subsequent recycling [Ecoembes 2021].

Alicante has joined to the **Circular Economy Club (CEC)**, which is a non-for-profit international network of circular economy professionals and organizations. Another initiative in Alicante is the **Sustainable Environmental Network (SEN)**, which is a leading digital platform that brings together solutions and professionals related to environmental sustainability. This start-up was launched on September 2017, and its objective is to look for synergies between different countries to help each other, facilitate communications and search for opportunities to live in a sustainable manner [SEN 2021]. Among the topics to be promoted by SEN are the circular economy, water and land management and environmental education.

SEN Innova, CEC, Universitat d'Alacant, AlicanTec, Torre Juana and FEMPA have joined to collaborate in order to identify the opportunities of the circular economy for the sustainable **urban development of Alicante**.

Aguas de Alicante (Municipal water utility of Alicante) has elaborated a new strategic plan for sustainable development, the **REwater Global Plan (2017-2021)**, with three main objectives: **Fighting climate change, preserving water as a source of life, and achieving energy self-sufficiency**. One of the projects to promote the **circular economy** is the installation Aqua Reuse Aeration System an innovative system that increases dissolved oxygen levels in water, avoiding water quality problems associated to reused water storage, with no need for energy supply.

7.1.2. Bodø, Norway

Regional level

International Development Norway (IDN) is a non-profit company with experience in international development projects, one of the research areas is the circular economy, which is based on: the design for close-loop production, water treatment and reuse, and analysis and advice for circular production (IDN 2021). One of the projects in which IDN has participated is the project of **Green Energy Roundtable**, which is meant to promote the discussions and spreading knowledge between Norway and Polish while creating a **roadmap for energy efficiency**. The main issues discussed during the Roundtables were:

- Effective resource management.
- Implementation of new technologies.
- Development of dispersed energy.
- Operational and management practices on a system level.
- Policies and regulations in the Polish energy system.

From the Norwegian side, the roundtable brought together representatives from the **Norwegian Water and Energy Directorate (NVE)**, the **Norwegian Environment Agency (ENOVA)**, the **Centre for Sustainable Energy Studies (CenSES)** and Innovation Norway, among others. Also, some month ago take place in Norway the **Nordic Circular Summit 2020**, co-hosted by **Nordic Innovation** and **Nordic Circular Hotspot**. It was an event to explore the circular opportunities that the region can offer. The sessions have been recorded and are available for the public in the Nordic Circular Summit platform [Nordic Circular Summit 2020].

Circular economy can play an important role in achieving Norway **Vision 2030**. This vision embraces the idea of making the **Nordic Region** the most sustainable and integrated region in the world by **2030**, and the co-operation in the Nordic Council of Ministers must serve this purpose. This includes, according to Paula Lehtomäki (Secretary General of the Nordic Council of Ministers), “**working for a green, competitive and inclusive Nordic Region, where circular economy can be a very central tool in achieving the target**”. Norway is looking for **innovative ways for sustainable use of resources**, a continuation is presented some of the developments based on the **circular economy** now:

- **Ocean Forest**, which was founded by Lerøy Seafood Group and the environmental organisation Bellona, is using phosphorous, nitrogen and CO₂ realised from fish farms to cultivate sugar kelp and mussels.
- **N₂ Applied**, which has developed a technology which able farmers to produce nitrogen fertiliser on their own farms by fixing it from air and reacting with ammonia found in the manure of their livestock.
- **Algae as a sustainable and circular resource for the future in Norway**

Algae can be used as a vector to achieve the transition to a circular economy. In Norway, there are some projects that are already working on that for example, **Finnfjord** is a ferrosilicon manufacturer in North Norway and is using algae farms to transform greenhouse gases to a resource. The start-up **AlgaePro** is working on a technology for cultivating microalgae using biowaste from municipal waste management, and **Ocean forest**, mentioned before, is another project related with the algae.

- Another company involved in the circular economy transition is **Repsol**, a Spanish energy and petrochemical company, which extract the hydrocarbon from the Norway reserves and has set a **Sustainability Plan (2020)**, where define some actions to contribute to sustainable development [Repsol 2020].
- **CityLoops** project brings together seven European cities like Bodø, to pilot a series of actions to close the loop of two of the most important waste flows in Europe, the construction and

demolition waste and biowaste. The aim is to become a circular city without any resource becoming a waste. This project is now developing a **Circular City Indicators** to guide the cities. The results will be published soon in the official website of the project.

Bodø Municipality

The municipality works with **circularity**, and then especially with planning the transformation of a military area into a new city district. There is ambition for **circular solutions** and the way of thinking will be more and more anchored in the administrations and amongst the skilled group of urban planners in the municipality – and of course also among their partners. For water the enough access is probably the reason why the municipality do not focus on reuse or efficiency. Topics as reuse of nature and building/constructions are also ambitioning for new city district.

The municipality has bold ambitions for an **energy system** for the future for the “New City – New airport”-development area. These areas shall have zero emissions of **greenhouse gasses** related to production, operations and transformation in a **life cycle perspective**. This entails amongst others **local renewable energy production**, and the sharing of energy between buildings in order to ensure flexibility in the energy system and lower pressure (peaks) on the grid. Moreover, important focus areas are the **optimisation of local energy systems** within a larger a larger system and responsive **energy efficient buildings**.

The existing airport area is transformed into a forward-looking new area with 15.000 new homes and 20.000 new jobs. A healthy, sustainable and vibrant place created to complement the existing city centre. Technicians ([Nordic Office Architecture](#)) have established site-wide strategies and created **toolboxes for circular synergies**, providing Bodø municipality with tools that will help them to realize their goals and ambitions for this **urban development** in the coming 50-100 years. Bodø - Circular City 2.0 - is the result of an inspiring collaboration between Nordic, BuroHappold, Felixx and KOHT. As the airport will be relocated, there are about 300 hectares to be transformed. **Collaboration and sharing key elements** of the strategy and untraditional links between functions can provide **synergies and added value for the entire city**. WP4 of B-WaterSmart will be aligned and in coordination with this strategy that propose three circular identities for Bodø: Sustainable industry and connectivity (Production of clean energy in interaction with other social functions and measures), Social robustness and adaptability (Workplaces created by new and innovative industries based on circular economy), and Natural Knowledge (Establish an interaction with nature that provides good outdoor spaces, sustainable food production, experiences and knowledge).

Bodø Municipality is thus a partner and pilot area in a national Norwegian research centre on **Zero Emission Neighbourhoods (ZEN)**. As one of eight pilot areas in the ZEN-centre, Bodø Municipality shall serve as an **innovation hub** where the ZEN researchers, together with building professionals, property developers, municipalities, energy companies and building owners and users test new solutions for the construction, operation, and use of neighbourhoods in order to reduce the greenhouse gas emissions to zero on a neighbourhood scale. The municipality is also a member of the ST Plan Action 3.2 Positive Energy District (PED) City Panel. This is also a network we actively participate in.

Energy supply

Norway is about **98% renewable** in its **power production** (94.3% hydro, 3.4% wind 2.3% other RES

in 2017). Moreover, a unique feature of the Norwegian power supply is the high share of flexible renewable production capacity (hydropower), i.e. 75%. Moreover, the large storage capacity (50% of Europe's reservoir storage capacity). Norway has the highest share of **Renewable energy sources** (RES) in its power supply in the EU and the lowest share of emissions in Europe, and we reached the EU 2020 RES-target as the first country in Europe.

Bodø Municipality is in an area with excess power-production. However, distribution grid remains a challenge in various parts of the region. Hence, in developing the **new urban area** the focus is placed on energy efficiency, reducing peak loads, constructing a robust and **sustainable energy system**. Efforts will be made to develop an **energy system** that relies on various sources of renewable energy, local renewable energy production, sharing energy within areas/neighbourhoods/districts and optimisation of local energy systems within a larger a **larger regional/national/Nordic/EU** energy system. Security of supply is at the core, as well as clean affordable energy for consumers.

With regards to electricity, Bodø municipality focus on local **renewable energy production**, and thus far technologies like **solar Photovoltaics** has been the one most included in projects. This, in combination with energy storage capacity, electric vehicles as a part of the energy system (V2G-technology) and other RES-technologies could be included in a microgrid. With a micro-grid, an area can function as flexibility reserves for the larger grid-area. Within the area, one can also make use of flexibility mechanisms, shave peaks and share energy within the microgrid area. Current legislation in **Norway does not allow for this set-up yet**, but it is believed that this the direction the development will take. Regarding the **thermal side**, a requirement will be that thermal power is generated from renewable sources. Thus, are solar thermal energy, geothermal energy, district heating/local heating based on RES, heat pump system and industrial waste heat all relevant sources of energy supply. The company in charge of the electricity, **Bodø Energi Group**, which is owned by the Bodø Municipality, is working for the development of the city in a sustainable way.

Bodø, which is closing the military airport and developing a new civilian one **has the opportunity to re-used and recycle the construction and demolition waste** to implement circular approaches. Other projects about circularity that are ongoing and where Bodø municipality participates are <https://www.circulus-project.de> Other highlight projects are at **nord university**, Bodø: <https://www.nord.no/en/studies/circular-economy-for-the-oil-gas-industry> and <https://www.nord.no/en/studies/master-of-science-in-global-management>.

7.1.3. East Frisia, Germany

The industrial structure in the supply area of the OOWV is largely made up of **small and medium-sized companies**. Existing large companies concentrate in the fields of **chemistry, plastics processing and food industry**. The production processes in these industries are both **energy and water intensive**. Increasing resource efficiency is a crucial task for companies not only from an ecological but also from an economic point of view in order to secure their competitiveness.

In the following environmental activities for some selected regional companies are described. The focus is on measures and concepts that can be assigned to the "**circular approach**" in the broadest sense.

Company: KENOW – Klärschlammentsorgung NordWest

- **URL:** <https://www.kenow-nordwest.de/>
- **Sector:** Sludge Treatment
- **Measures:** A mono-processing plant is being built in Bremen for the thermal utilization of sewage sludge. The plant is designed for a capacity of around 55,000 t dry matter. As a result, significantly less sewage sludge is spread directly on the fields and the soil, groundwater and drinking water are protected. From 2029, agricultural disposal will be prohibited as a matter of principle. The plant will be energy-autonomous and almost climate-neutral. It will also be connected to the district heating network. A modern and highly effective flue gas cleaning system ensures that no pollutants or odors are emitted. The plant also produces ash. Over 90 % phosphorus can be recovered from this. Until phosphorus recycling plants are ready for the market, the ash will be stored in landfills.

Company: OOWV

- **URL:** <https://www.oowv.de/wissen/abwasser/projekte/erlaeuterungen-zum-projekt-faultuerme/>
- **Sector:** Sludge Treatment
- **Measures:** Expansion of the Oldenburg wastewater treatment plant. Construction of two digestion towers to increase the storage capacity for sludge treatment; Conversion of the existing small digester to a covered digested sludge storage tank; Use of energy-optimized plant technology and energy-efficient motors; Renewal of the digested sludge heating and heating sludge circulation system. With this central sewage sludge disposal concept and the energetic utilization of the sewage gas, it is aimed an independent energy supply of the sewage treatment plant. This also results in a CO₂ reduction to protect the climate and the environment.

Company: DKM Molkerei Edeweicht

URL: <https://www.dmk.de/wer-wir-sind/geschaeftsbericht-2019/nachhaltigkeit-verantwortung/#c12993>

- **Sector:** Dairy
- **Measures:** Sustainability as a central principle; environmental management system according to ISO 14001 and energy management system according to ISO 50001; generation and consumption of the energy used as well as optimization in wastewater disposal and recycling; flexible and profitable inclusion of the cold store in the energy market is in planning; in addition, considerable water savings have been achieved in recent years through various individual measures (e.g. substitution of fresh water by condensates).

7.1.4. Flanders, Belgium

In Belgium, the Federal Public Services of Public Health and Economy have been integrated into the external working group "**actors of the waste policy**" of the European Consumer Centre in order to provide a forum for exchange between the federal and **regional levels of government and business**

federations, with a view to strengthening the coherence of waste policies. In the Brussels Region, the **Programme for the Circular Economy 2016-20 is co-ordinated** by three ministers and four regional administrative bodies (Government of the Brussels-Capital Region, 2016).

In Flanders Region (2018), the **Public Waste Agency of Flanders (OVAM)** set up a national platform for the circular economy, through which the top levels of federal and **regional environment departments, economy/innovation departments and finance departments** meet twice a year to take decisions in priority policy fields. Government of Flanders has determined the circular economy as one of the seven transition priorities of the region and has assigned the **OVAM** as the initiator of the Circular Flanders [v.circular 2021]. OVAM is responsible for waste management and soil remediation in Flanders.

Circular Flanders (*Vlaanderen Circulair*) is the centre of the circular economy in Flanders is a partnership of public authorities, companies, civil society and research institutions created in 2016 and the knowledge community. In the cross-cutting policy paper “Vision 2050. A long-term strategy for Flanders”, the Flemish government has defined six key activities: building networks and co-operation among stakeholders; reducing experimentation risks in the circular economy; developing research through the Policy Research Centre for the Circular Economy; fostering policy co-ordination; stimulating innovation and entrepreneurship; and up-scaling circular economy projects. There focus areas are: Circular Flanders has three pillars of action: Circular Procurement, Circular Business, and Circular City.

The seven priority transition areas for **Flanders towards 2025**, have been impulse by the **Flemish Council for Science and Innovation** (*Vlaamse Raad voor Wetenschap en Innovative*, VRWI) and **involve over 230 stakeholders from industry, research, government, and civil society**. Based on major societal challenges, each transition area presents a set of science, technology, and innovation priorities, creating the business opportunities of tomorrow. These seven areas are [V. R. v. W. e. Innovatie, 2014]: Digital society, Food, Health and Well-Being, Smart Resource Management, Urban Planning Mobility, Mobility Dynamics, and Logistics, New Energy Demand and delivery, Society.

Circular Procurement

The **Green Deal on Circular Procurement** was set up in 2017 in collaboration with The Shift, the Flemish Association of Cities and Municipalities and the *Bond Beter Leefmilieu*. From 2017 to 2019, it has been registered 115 circular procurement projects. The **green deal** is a voluntary agreement between (private) partners and the Flemish government to start a green project together [D. OMGEVING, 2021].

In this sense, in 2018, it was started the **Procirc**, a transnational North Sea Region project, which aims to reduce raw material use and the emission of waste and CO₂ by 20 to 25% [C. Flanders,2017].

A	B	C	D	E
 Maximise the reusability or recyclability of materials				
A 1 Internal sharing	B 1 Understanding the share of recycled, biobased and virgin materials present	C 1 Extending guarantees	D 1 Design for Disassembly	E 1 Design for recycling
A 2 Renting or peer to peer sharing	B 2 Increasing the amount of recycled content	C 2 Contractual arrangements for maintenance and repair	D 2 Modular design	E 2 Understanding materials
A 3 Reuse, refurbishing or upgrading	B 3 Increasing the amount of biobased content	C 3 Upgradable products	D 3 Standardised design	E 3 Contractual arrangements for take back and recycling
A 4 Minimal use of materials in design		C 4 Design for longevity	D 4 Understanding the internal composition and connections	E 4 Reducing or banning toxicity
A 5 Less waste		C 5 Repairability and maintainability	D 5 Contractual arrangements for take back and reuse	E 5 Biologically degradable / compostable
GOALS AND STRATEGIES FOR CIRCULAR PURCHASERS 		C 6 Modular/change oriented design	D 6 Stimulate circular business models	E 6 Stimulate circular business models
		C 7 Contractual incentives for extension of useful life		
		C 8 Supplier guidance for use optimization		

Figure 19: Goals and strategies for Circular Procurement projects.

Source: [C. Flanders, 2017].

Circular Business

Constructions in Flanders represents a huge material impact, about 30 to 40% of the **waste** comes from the construction industry, and for that reason it was started the **Green Deal of Construction**. Circular construction economy is based on smarter designs, products and materials reutilization and residual waste minimization.

There are three main objectives: **Change in the design, construction and/or dismantling practice; adapting the business model to create social value in addition to financial profit; develop, share, apply and adjust knowledge, data and practical experience through partnerships** [C. Flanders, 2017].

Tracimat is a Flemish example of demolition management which evaluates the use of materials and hazardous substances (e.g. asbestos) released during dismantling and demolition work in order to recycle with high efficiency.

Circular Cities

Since 2017, Circular Flanders/OVAM has participated in the **Circular Economy Urban Agenda**, coordinated by the city of Oslo and its aim is to create a more relevant connection between its policy and the specific needs and solutions of cities and their citizens (C. Flanders, 2017). At the end of 2018, the association presented the **final action plan** [Urban agenda 2018], to be implemented from 2019.

Smart cities

IMEC (**Interuniversity Microelectronics Centre**) is leading the research and development of smart cities in Flanders. Some of the projects that is supporting are [F. I. a. trade 2021] [IMEC 2021]:

- **SELECT for Cities:** A European initiative to develop an innovation and technology platform to help transform cities into large-scale testing grounds for IoT experiments.
- **City of Things:** A project to bring the Internet of Things to the city of Antwerp (Flanders), turning it into a living lab as well as a real-time open data platform.
- **Capital of Things:** An extension of the previous project. In this case, the city of Antwerp, its port, its University and the IMEC, collaborate to establish an IoT ecosystem. The port of Antwerp will collaborate with the data platform **NxtPort** and the private port companies in a "Harbor of Things".

All these projects are carried out with data gathered by sensors, chips and networks scattered around the cities.

Circular metabolism

Metabolic studies research flows of materials, water, sediment, energy, food, air, biomass, data in a city or region, and then, these flows are mapped [C. Flanders, 2017].

The project '**The Metabolism of Antwerp, a City of Flows**' is based on nine types of flows in and around Antwerp and is focused on the opportunities they offer to prepare Antwerp for a future as a circular city.

Circular ports

All Flemish port authorities have made the circular economy a top priority.

Architecture Workroom Brussels and **1010au** mapped the circular potential of the city's ports with a reference of 11 European city ports [C. Flanders, 2017].

Circular economy projects relevant for B-Watersmart in the Flemish region

This lists focusses on types of projects rather than specific individual projects.

- **Alternative water resources:** different projects focus on alternative, sustainable water resources. Water users include drinking water companies, nature, agriculture and industry. Those alternative resources include desalination of brackish water, rain water harvesting and various types of ground water recharge. More relevant specific types are detailed below.
- Check for instance the website of the [Fresh4Cs project](#) where managed aquifer recharge and treatment of RO concentrate are demonstrated.
- A new brackish water desalination installation for drinking water position has been constructed in Oostende. Check [press article](#).

Water use efficiency increase and internal water reuse are rather common practices in Flemish industries, especially in water intensive industries such as the clothes washing industry, chemical

industry, food processing industry and drinks producing industries.

- One example is [the DUWAHE project](#), that has increased water efficiency and started internal water reuse in beer brewing industries
- The [EColoRO project](#) has focused on water reuse in the textile sector.
- **Water reuse from communal or industrial WWTP:** valorisation of WWTP effluent for other purposes is increasingly popular, although still not common. Key projects are (but there are many other):
 - Since 2002, IWVA is reusing WWTP for aquifer recharge (coastal dunes) and drinking water production, based on RO. Check for instance these [slides](#) or their Dutch-language [website](#).
 - The [F2AGRI project](#) got lots of attention over the last years. Here industrial effluent (from a food processing plant) is fed into an irrigation system that irrigates local farmland.
 - In Nieuwe Dokken (Gent), grey water from a new city district is reused by a nearby industry. Check [website](#) in Dutch and [English](#).
 - The [WAVE project](#) focused on water reuse at festivals, with the development of tools and strategies that can later on be applied in households or elsewhere.
- **Recuperation of materials from waste water** is rather new in Flanders, with only a few examples.

In Nieuwe Dokken (Gent), energy is harvested from waste water, while also nutrients (P, N) are being recuperated. Check [website](#) in Dutch and [English](#).

7.1.5. Lisbon, Portugal

In the sense of a smart sustainable cities, **Lisbon Strategic Plan for Circular Economy** aims to reach three vertical areas: energy, water, and materials. Preliminary documents have been defined and supported within the energy and water issues. A matrix for the materials of the Lisbon metropolitan area is also now available. Key projects currently underway in the city [SS Cities 2020]:

Water

Strategic Plan for the Reuse of Lisbon City Water is a partnership between the Lisbon City Council and Águas do Tejo Atlântico. With this project, the city aims to save 3 million m³ of drinking water by 2030.

Energy

Lisbon Solar City (*Lisboa Cidade Solar*) is a solar strategy approved by the municipality in June 2018 in the framework of the covenant of Mayors for Climate and Energy. Based on this strategy, it has been set a series of goals.

SOLIS, which is supposed to be the foundation of this strategy, is a platform to offer citizens, local authorities, investors, and businesses the possibility to gather information on solar energy potential in

the city [E Cities 2020]. SOLIS has been launched by the **Energy and Environment Agency of Lisbon and** gives citizens the opportunity to be involved in the local energy system.

Materials

Several initiatives are being implemented in Lisbon to reduce the production of bio-waste and increase the circularity of food.

Another initiative underway in Lisbon is the **Sustainable Food Production and Management**. Since, 2010, Lisbon has made a strong commitment to prevent food waste in order to reduce its associated footprint on natural resources. The city has launched a number of initiatives which are focused on measures to collect and reduce food waste while supporting local initiatives or citizens' movements [EG Capital]. One of these movements is **ReFood**, a project started in 2011 to promote the prevention of food waste, it collects surplus food donations from restaurants and businesses and delivers it to the needy at local level [re-food 2021].

In addition, Lisbon is part of the **Circular economy club**.

Waste

Waste reduction and more efficient and optimal use of resources are key goals in the majority of strategies hereby assessed, with expected positive impacts on the environment and the economy. Among the main environmental goals, waste reduction is the most prominent (e.g. France, the Netherlands, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain).

Portugal has carried out extensive dialogue with public entities managing waste, waste management operators, the Portuguese Water Partnership (PPA), the Portuguese Soil Partnership (PPS), water resource planners, river basin managers, water sector managers, irrigator associations, the National Commission to Fight Food Waste and the Directorate General of Food and Veterinary Medicine.

Region

On one hand, the Portuguese Council of Ministers publish in 2017, in the Journal of the Portuguese Government, the "**Leading the transition: a circular economy action plan for Portugal**" (2017-2020)"

One of the components of the action plan of the Ministry of Environment for the circular economy is the portal ECO.NOMIA, which has the objective to make public the advantages and opportunities of financing to consumers and companies and start an interactive forum for collaborative investments projects in Circular Economy. Some of the projects gathered in ECO.NOMIA are:

- 100etiqueta: is a circular economy platform for parents and babies.
- MyCloma and Auchan: Auchan Retail Portugal has partnered with MyCloma, an online platform for selling second-hand clothing, to combat textile waste and promote the circular economy.

On the other hand, the **Environmental Fund** (*Fundo Ambiental*), which is a financial tool to support the environmental policy of the government, has started the **Program for the preparation of studies on bio-waste collection systems**. This program aims to provide municipalities with financing for the transition to selective collection of bio-waste. In a circular bioeconomy, recycling bio-waste is crucial to optimise the use of biomass [E Fund 2021].

Moreover, the Portuguese Environment Agency developed in 2019 a preliminary study on the implementation of selective collection in Portugal, focusing on the bio-waste management.

Another initiative in Portugal is the investment platform **GoParity**, which promote sustainable projects by facilitating access to new ethical opportunities [Go Parity 2021]. Some of the projects published in this platform are:

- Circular Biofuels: This project valuate used cooking oils through its reutilization.
- Circular light steel: Light steel is recycled through fusion to create other steel products.
- Lisbon vertical farm: The aim of Reculture is to bring vertical farms in Europe to allow cities to grow food in a sustainable and profitable way

7.1.6. Venice, Italy

In Italy, the circular economy strategic framework positions on the issue, in continuity with the commitments adopted under the Paris Climate Change Agreement, the UN Agenda 2030 on Sustainable Development, the G7 Communiqué and within the EU. The circular economy strategy is part of the implementation of the wider National Strategy for Sustainable Development in Italy, adopted in 2017, contributing to the objectives of more efficient use of resources and more circular and sustainable patterns of production and consumption.

ENEA, the Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development, and the **Circular Economy Network in Italy**, presented in 2019, the **National Report on the Circular Economy in Italy** with 10 proposals to promote the development of the circular economy in Italy. The Circular Economy Network is promoted by the Foundation for sustainable development and by 14 companies and business associations.

Proposals from the CE Network⁷ are:

1. Spread and enrich the vision, knowledge, research, and good practices of a circular economy.
2. Implement a national strategy and action plan for a circular economy.
3. Improve the use of economic instruments for a circular economy.
4. Promote a regenerative bioeconomy.
5. Extend circular economy to public procurement.

⁷ <https://circulareconomynetwork.it/>

6. Promote the initiative of cities for a circular economy.
7. Ensure a rapid and effective implementation of the new European directives on waste and circular economy.
8. Rapidly activate an effective end of waste regulation: an essential tool for a circular economy.
9. Ensure the necessary infrastructure for a circular economy.
10. Extend circular economy also to online commerce (e-commerce).

ENEA has also promoted the creation of the **Italian Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform (ICESP)**, which aims to compare and gather the different initiatives about Circular Economy underway in Italy, to promote information to the public and identify the best practices.

The Ministry of Environment, Land and Sea (MATTM) and the Ministry of Economic Development (MISE), published in 2017 the document **Towards a circular economy model for Italy** with aim of providing a general framework for circular economy [MATTM, MISE; 2021]. Some of the key measures and the intervention areas proposed are the followings:

1. Ecological design
2. Development of secondary raw material markets
3. Adopting more sustainable patterns of consumption
4. Waste management

Moreover, the MATTM and the MISE, with the support of ENEA have also presented a technical **“Work Table”** with the aim of identifying suitable indicators to measure and monitor the circularity of the economy and the efficient use of resources at the macro, meso and micro level [MATTM, MISE; 2021].

Another initiative carried out in Italy is the union of **Enel** and **Symbola Foundation**, that presented in March 2018 the research **“100 Italian Circular Economy Stories”**, a map of 100 Italian realities that operate in the circular economy field [Enel, Symbola; 2018].

Polices and laws

Italy has approved a series of polices and laws to promote the Circular Economy in the country. For example, the **Law 221 of 28 of December 2015** and **legislative decrees** that define guidelines and criteria, such as the calculation of the rate of differentiated collection for municipal solid waste or the criteria for the eco-design of WEEE (Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment) [Ghisellini et al. 2019].

Law 221 was presented by the **Ministry of environment** to promote green economy measures and to limit the excessive use of natural resources. The article 18 of the law, declare that is mandatory for the Italian public entities to include minimum environmental criteria (MIC) in their public procurement actions [ED Association 2020].

Examples of initiatives in Venice

ENI, Italian Multinational Oil and Gas company

Eni is leading the change of traditional refineries into bio-refineries. For now, this has been implemented in Venice and Gela. The idea is to produce biofuels through a feedstock of 100% of second-generation raw materials [Eni 2021].

In the chemicals sectors, Eni is transforming recycled polymers into secondary raw materials by diversification of feedstock and eco-design in order to maximize resource efficiency.

Also, they cooperate with other companies in order to collect used cooking oil and supply Hydrotreated Vegetable Oils biofuel. Companies like AMA in Rome, Veritas in Venice, Hera in Modena and AMAT in Taranto.

Venice International University

The University is developing research and projects focused on the policies and strategies to move to a green economy and low-carbon society in line with the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable development. [V. I. University].

Examples of the Italian Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform

Projects in Venice:

Ca' Foscari University of Venice is working on a project based on the extraction of natural dyes from the residues derived from winemaking that can capture solar energy through a PV solar cell to produce energy.

Projects in Italy:

- **Fortunale** is a sweater company which is entirely eco-friendly and is based on circular economy concepts.
- **Legno Urbano** is a project to take profit and promote wood recovery from the trees which are felled in urban areas.
- **Rigiocattolo** is an initiative to collect used toys and give them a second life by regenerating them.
- **Life DOP project** is based on the utilization of livestock waste to produce renewable energy and fertilisers (solid digestate) through anaerobic digestion and then, this digestate is exported to non-livestock areas.

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